

Flora of the Biloozerskyi National Nature Park (Kyiv and Cherkasy Oblasts, Ukraine): annotated checklist, analysis and regional features

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Abstract: The Biloozerskyi National Nature Park is a significant protected area in the Left-Bank Forest-Steppe of Ukraine and includes forest, wetland, and aquatic ecosystems. The flora of this park was shaped by the combined influence of natural components of the northern mixed (oak-pine) forest and forest-steppe zones, which makes it unique compared to other nature protected areas in the region. The study revealed the presence of 851 species and subspecies of vascular plants on this territory, of which 684 are native and 167 are alien. For the first time, alien plant species *Rubus balticus* has been included in the list of the flora of Ukraine. The most representative families are Asteraceae, Poaceae, Cyperaceae, Rosaceae, Caryophyllaceae and Lamiaceae. The most species-rich genera are *Carex*, *Veronica*, *Trifolium* and *Pilosella*. Geographic analysis of the flora indicates the dominance of widespread species (48.6 %) among native plants, as well as European (17.8 %) and Euro-Mediterranean (13.4 %) zonal elements. In contrast, the alien fraction is mainly represented by species of Mediterranean (46.7 %) and American (23.4 %) origin. The biomorphological structure of the native flora is characterized by a predominance of perennials (65.2 %), whereas the alien fraction includes a larger proportion of annuals, biennials and short-lived (60.5 %). Meadow-steppe, forest, and wetland plant communities play a crucial role in shaping the floristic composition of the park. The highest species richness is observed in pine forests, meadow steppes, and in riparian ecosystems. The flora of the park has significant conservation value, as 107 rare and endangered species have been identified, 25 of which are listed in

the Red Data Book of Ukraine. At the same time, 35 invasive species have been recorded, such as *Acer negundo*, *Asclepias syriaca*, *Solidago canadensis* and *Robinia pseudoacacia*, which pose a threat to natural plant communities.

Keywords: biodiversity, protected area, native plants, rare species, alien species, conservation.

Introduction

The study of biodiversity, particularly flora, in national nature parks and reserves is of great importance due to the critical role these territories play in preserving natural environments (Haight & Hammill 2020). One of the important nature conservation areas in the central region of Ukraine is the Biloozerskyi National Nature Park (hereinafter – the Park), located on the left bank of the Dnipro River. The flora of this territory is of exceptional value due to the combination of vegetation of the Forest-Steppe zone with intrazonal elements of the more northern Mixed-Forest zone, which together form a kind of “island” of natural biodiversity in an anthropogenically transformed landscape. Studying the floristic diversity of this area is essential for understanding regional biodiversity patterns, conserving rare species, and assessing the impact of global climate change in Central Ukraine (Rakhmetov & Zaimenko 2022; Didukh 2023).

Territorial features and history of establishment

The park is an extremely interesting territory with well-preserved natural habitats, encompassing the second (sandy) terrace of the Dnipro River (which is covered by pine and oak-pine forests), the second terrace (covered by oak forests), swamp and steppe areas on slopes. Covering an area of 7,014.44 hectares, the Park is located on the left bank of the Kaniv Reservoir, within the administrative boundaries of Boryspil raion of the Kyiv Oblast and Cherkasy raion of the Cherkasy Oblast (Fig. 1). Unlike many other high-ranking protected areas in Ukraine, the Park's territory is spatially continuous (Shynder et al. 2023; Bezsmertna et al. 2024; Kolomiychuk et al. 2024b).

According to the physical-geographical zoning, the park is located within the Dnipro lowland (Marynych et al. 2003). In the geobotanical zoning of Ukraine, this territory belongs to the Left-Bank Dnipro natural district of linden-oak, hornbeam-oak and pine (on terraces) forests, meadows, halophyte and wetland vegetation of the Forest-Steppe subprovince (Didukh & Shelyag-Sosonko 2003). In the historical-geographical aspect, this territory is also known as the Middle Dnipro region (its localized name is "Serednye Prydniprovyia") (Chopyk et al. 1998).

The earliest records of plants from the area that may now be within the boundaries of Biloozerskyi National Nature Park were provided by A. Rogowicz (1869) from the vicinity of Khotsky village, such as *Delphinium cuneatum* Spreng. and *Drosera rotundifolia* L. A more detailed characterization of the local flora, before the landscape transformation (during the Soviet period, the Dnipro Valley was flooded with the aim of creating the Kaniv Reservoir), can be drawn from the descriptions by

J. Paczoski (1894) of the vegetation around Pereiaslav town, located 14 km northwest of the Park. Among other observations, this author described a pine forest that has been preserved about 3 km northwest of the Park. He noted the remarkable diversity of the flora, as a relatively small area contained a significant number of

Fig. 1 Location and boundaries of the Biloozerskyi National Nature Park.

phytocoenoses with rich floristic composition. Many of the described plant communities were characterized for the northern Mixed-Forest zone (this is known in Eastern Europe as Polissya) and markedly different from the coenoses of the adjacent forest-steppe terraces of Dnipro, indicating their intrazonal origin.

Before the creation of the Kaniv Reservoir, the Dnipro River flowed along approximately 8.5–9.5 km from the modern boundaries of the Park, while the entire intervening area was occupied by a swampy floodplain with numerous water bodies (the first terrace of the Dnipro River). Fragments of these wetland complexes have been preserved in ancient alluvial depressions within the central (axial) part of the Park. The hydrological regime of these depressions is complex, fed by both groundwater from the sandy terrace and surface runoff. Additionally, the water level of the Kaniv Reservoir, which fluctuates between 87 and 93 m above sea level (Shevchyk et al. 2021), is closely aligned with those of the Park's wetlands and Bile Lake (89–92 m a.s.l.). Due to a connecting channel that unites them into a single wetland system, a slow water exchange occurs through reverse flow fluctuations in the Kaniv Reservoir and infiltration through the sandy deposits. Due to water seepage from the Kaniv Reservoir through permeable sandy deposits, certain coastal depressions within the territory of the park have become swampy. As a result, both primary and secondary swamps have formed, which had a favorable impact on the spread of the marsh vegetation.

The history of the Park's establishment dates back to the 1990s when T.L. Andriyenko and M.L. Klyestov proposed the creation of the Pereiaslavskyyi National Nature Park, covering approximately 24,000 hectares. However, this project was never implemented (Fedoronchuk et al. 2004; Yarova 2012, 2015; Yarova & Fedoronchuk 2013). The current National Nature Park was established in 2009 only (Yarova 2012). The Park's land cover is dominated by forest areas (97.3 %), with only 2.7 % consisting of water bodies (33 ha) and wetlands (117.9 ha) (Shevchyk et al. 2024b).

Since its establishment, the Park's vegetation cover has been studied by M.M. Fedoronchuk, N.I. Kretsul and O.A. Yarova, who documented the rare species known within the Park at that time (Kretsul 2011; Yarova 2012), analyzed the structure of the Park's flora (Yarova & Fedoronchuk 2013, 2014, 2015), and examined the status and characteristics of the synanthropic fraction of the flora (Yarova 2012; Yarova & Kretsul 2019), as well as forest (Yarova 2017), aquatic and wetland vegetation (Yarova & Kretsul 2019). V.L. Shevchyk and co-authors discovered new localities of rare species such as *Aldrovanda vesiculosa* L., *Lycopodium annotinum* L. and *Utricularia minor* L. within the Park (Shevchyk et al. 2024a, b) and conducted research on the vegetation of Bile Lake (Shevchyk et al. 2023). Additionally, H.A. Chorna and co-authors recorded the first occurrence of the alien aquatic plant *Elodea nuttallii* in Ukraine near the territory of the Park (Chorna et al. 2006).

In 2015, 522 plant species were known from the Park's territory, and an additional 76 species were indicated as potentially occurring in this area in the future (Yarova 2015). It was established that species with temperate (55.9 %) and boreal (33.8 %)

distribution patterns predominated in the geographical structure (Yarova & Fedoronchuk 2014, 2015). But over the last decade, according to research by V.L. Shevchyk and co-authors, a large number of plants which are new for the Park's flora have been discovered here and it indicates the potential for further discoveries and the need for a new stage of floristic inventory (Shevchyk et al. 2024b).

Methodology

The annotated checklist of the flora was compiled based on critically reviewed literature sources (Yarova 2012, 2015; Yarova & Fedoronchuk 2013; Yarova & Kretsul 2019) and the results of our own field studies conducted in 2022–2024. The identification of collected vascular plant specimens was conducted using identification keys (Prokudin et al. 1977; Prokudin 1987; Mosyakin 1996; Tichomirov 2000; Bräutigam & Greuter 2007; Olshanskyi 2010; Boiko 2011; Rothmaler 2017). Specimens of selected plants were deposited in the KW and KWHA herbaria.

The nomenclature of vascular plants follows the Plants of the World Online database (<https://powo.science.kew.org/>). Higher taxa of the lycophytes, ferns (including horsetails) and gymnosperms are listed at the subclasses and family's level according to (Christenhusz et al. 2011a, b). The families of flowering plants are listed according to the APG IV system (2016). In addition to accepted species and subspecies of the spontaneous flora, the checklist includes several nothospecies, varieties and ergasiophytes from the Park's forest plantations that have not yet become naturalized. A list of casual ergasiophygophytes recorded near the Park's boundaries, particularly at a nearby landfill sites, is also provided.

For the analysis of the floristic structure, characteristics of monotypic species and subspecies of polytypic plant species spontaneously occurring within the Park were used. The native and alien plants were analyzed separately. The systematic analysis followed standard principles (Szafer 1952; Khokhryakov 2000). The geographical analysis was conducted according to the botanical-geographical features, with the assignment of local plants to a specific geographical element (according to its natural range) and the identification of alien plant origin (Szafer 1952; Kleopov 1990; Protopopova 1991; Davydov 2021). The basic scheme of geographical elements is the classification of Yu.D. Kleopov (1990) with several clarifications. Thus, the Euro-Mediterranean geographical element is separately distinguished, to which we have attributed species widely distributed both in the Mediterranean and in the temperate zone of Europe. These species (for example *Campanula rapunculus* L.) combine the characteristics of the European and Mediterranean geographical elements. The nomadic type of geoelement in the sense of Kleopov (1990) is divided here into the Eurasian steppe and Eurasian north-steppe (according to Nosova 1973) geographical elements. The South Siberian type of geoelement is indicated here as Euro-Siberian. The biomorphological analysis was based on a structural-morphological approach, distinguishing life forms (Clements 1920, with the differentiation of individual biomorphological groups of lianas, and aquatic plants,

according to Serebryakova 1974), as well as an ecological-biological approach (Raunkiaer 1907).

Alien plant species were classified according to their mode of immigration as xenophytes and ergasiophygophytes (Pyšek et al. 2004). Rare plant species were identified based on their inclusion in several conservation lists (Bern Convention 2011; Bilz et al. 2011; Order 111).

The ecological-phytocoenotic analysis of the flora was based on the participation of plants within nine major habitat groups in the Park (classification by Didukh et al. 2011):

Group I – Eutrophic and mesotrophic water bodies (includes: C1 – stagnant and flowing freshwater bodies in the classification by Didukh et al. 2011).

Group II – Eutrophic wetlands and riparian vegetation (includes: D1 – riparian vegetation with stable or highly variable moisture regimes on muddy and sandy substrates; G1.111, 112, 114, 115 – riverine flooded willow-poplar forests and shrublands; G1.132 – eutrophic alder swamp forests).

Group III – Mesotrophic sedge, shrub, and forested bogs (includes: D2 – permanently wet peat bogs; G1.121–122 – swampy and moist birch forests and woodlands; G1.131 – alder swampy sphagnum forests and woodlands).

Group IV – Fresh shady oak forests (includes: G1.2 – shady broadleaf forests and shrublands on rich soils).

Group V – Light, fresh, and moist pine and mixed (oak-pine) forests (includes: G1.123-124 – light small-leaved mesic forests on moderately rich and poor soils; G1.211, 216, 217 – oak forests of the pine terrace; G2.214 – green-moss pine forests; G3.11 – pine-oak and derivative acidophilous oak forests on moderately rich, weakly podzolic soils).

Group VI – Meadow steppes and derived shrublands and derived woodlands (includes: E2 – meadow-steppe vegetation on chernozems; F3 – shrublands replacing meadow steppes; G1.3 – woodlands and shrublands replacing meadow steppes).

Group VII – Fresh and moist meadows, forest edges (includes: E1 – grass meadows on fresh turf soils; E4 – glades and forest edges dominated by perennial herbs; F2 – *Rubus* thickets on moderately rich, fresh soils).

Group VIII – Dry pine woodlands and open sandy areas (includes: E3 – sandy wastelands; G2.215-216 – pine woodlands with epigeic lichen cover and steppe-like herbaceous layers on sands).

Group IX – Synantropic biotopes (includes: I2 – ruderal grassland biotopes; I3 – biotopes formed after forest clearings; I4 – artificial forest biotopes).

The analysis considered the biotope range and distribution types of 834 vascular plant species personally verified by the authors, with many species assigned to multiple coenofloras simultaneously. This approach enabled an objective characterization of the identified coenofloras and revealed the role of different geographic elements in their genesis.

Results

Floristic structure

As a result of the survey, 851 vascular plant taxa (species and subspecies) were recorded in the park. Compared with the previous inventory (Yarova & Fedoronchuk 2013; Yarova 2015), the list was increased to 329 taxa over the past decade. However, it should be noted that among the added species at least 56 are those that Yarova (2015) indicated as potentially occurring. The current checklist therefore comprises 42.4 % of the 2 009 taxa so far reported for the Middle Dnipro region (Chopyk et al. 1998, now partly outdated). Thus, the Park's flora is highly representative of the region's vascular plant diversity.

A comparison of the taxonomic richness of the Park's flora with that of other, significantly larger, special protected areas in Central Ukraine and adjacent regions (Tab. 1) demonstrates that its diversity is above average. The documented flora of the Park holds significant value at the national level. During our study, we recorded *Rubus balticus* (Focke) E.H.L. Krause, an alien bramble species which is new for the flora of Ukraine. Additionally, from this section of the Dnipro water area near the Park's territory, the neophyte *Elodea nuttallii* (Planch.) H.St. John has been firstly reported for the flora of Ukraine (Chorna et al. 2006). Moreover, several plant species in the Park are extremely rare for the Forest-Steppe zone of Ukraine, such as *Lycopodium annotinum* L., *Onoclea struthiopteris* (L.) Roth, *Tephrosieris integrifolia* (L.) Holub and *Thesium ebracteatum* Hayne. The state of the habitat of these species and their population size require a separate detail study. During this research, for the first time in the Forest-Steppe zone of Ukraine, a little-known notospecies of the flora of Ukraine was discovered - *Utricularia xneglecta* Lehm. This plant was listed for the western region of Ukraine as *U. australis* auct. non R.Br. (the true *U. australis* is found now in Australasia only), but it was recently discovered in northern regions of Ukraine, which indicates the wider distribution of this species (Iakushenko & Orlov 2015).

From a territorial point of view, almost all of the park's floristic wealth – 835 taxa (98.12 %) – has been recorded in its northern part, located within the Kyiv Oblast. An additional 13 species, reported by Yarova (2015), were also most likely recorded in this part of the Park. At the same time, in the southern part of the Park, within the Cherkasy Oblast, only 632 taxa (74.26 %) have been documented so far. This discrepancy is explained by the fact that all habitat types present in the Park are fully represented within Kyiv Oblast.

As is typical for Temperate-zone floras, the largest number of species in the Park belongs to the clade Eudicots, particularly within the adventive fraction, while other taxonomic groups are significantly less represented (Tab. 2).

The studied flora includes a well-represented diversity of ferns, horsetails and lycophytes, which are characteristic of boreal vegetation and are primarily found in Polissia in Ukraine. Therefore, the studied flora of the Park is similar to the flora of the Zalissia National Nature Park, located precisely in the mixed-forest zone, in

Tab. 1 Comparison of the taxonomic richness of the Biloozerskyi National Nature Park flora with other special protected areas of the mixed-forest (Polissia) and forest-steppe zones of Ukraine. Abbreviation: NNP – National Nature Park, NR – Nature Reserve.

Protected Area	Area (ha)	Total number of plants
Mixed-forest zone (Polissia)		
Cheremskyi NR	2975.7	760 (Konishchuk 2006)
Chornobyl Radiation-Ecological Biosphere Reserve	226964.7	1290 (Kolomiychuk 2022)
Desniansko-Starohutskyi NNP	16215.1	853 (Panchenko 2014)
Drevlianskyi NR	30872.84	965 (Orlov 2024)
Mezynskyi NNP	31035.2	772 (Karpenko 2016)
Poliskyi NR	20104	754 (Orlov et al. 2015)
Prypiat-Stokhid NNP	39315.5	over 600 (Andriyenko et al. 2009)
Rivne NR	42288.7	627 (Danylyk et al. 2019)
Shatskyi NNP	48976.6	868 (Fitsailo & Pashkevych 2013)
Tsumanska Puscha NNP	33475.34	889 (Bezsmertna et al. 2024)
Zalissia NNP	14836	778, with additions – 785 (Kolomiychuk et al. 2024a, b)
Forest-steppe zone		
Biloozerskyi NNP	7014.44	851
Dvorichanskyi NNP	3131.2	721 (Petrovych et al. 2014)
Hetmanskyi NNP	23360.1	635 (Onyshchenko & Andriyenko 2012b)
Holosiivskyi NNP	10988.14	752 (Onyshchenko et al. 2016)
Homilshanski Lisy NNP	14314.8	864 (Onyshchenko & Andriyenko 2012b)
Ichnyanskyi NNP	9665.8	680 (http://ichn-park.in.ua/?p=8907)
Kaniv NR	2027	995 (Shechyk et al. 1996; Onyshchenko & Andriyenko 2012a)
Kholodnyi Yar NNP	6 833.5071	428 (Shynder et al. 2023)
Karmeliukove Podillia NNP	16518	around 1000 (Markivska 2014)
Mykhailivska Tsilyna NR	882.9	531 (Onyshchenko & Andriyenko 2012a)
Nyzhniosulskyi NNP	18635.11	over 600 (Onyshchenko & Andriyenko 2012b)
Pyriatynskyi NNP	12028.42	1174 (Kovalenko 2016)
Slobzhanskyi NNP	5244	818 (Bezrodnova 2017)

Tab. 2 Systematic structure of the Biloozerskyi National Nature Park flora.

Taxonomic group	Native plants		Alien plants		Total
	Number of taxa	%	Number of taxa	%	
Lycopodiidae	2	0.3	-	-	2
Equisetidae	6	0.9	-	-	6
Ophioglossidae	2	0.3	-	-	2
Polypodiidae	12	1.8	-	-	12
Gymnospermae	2	0.3	1	0.6	3
Angiospermae	660	96.4	166	99.4	826
in part.: Basal angiosperms s.l.	5	0.6	-	-	5
Monocots	165	24.1	26	14.6	191
Eudicots	490	71.7	140	84.8	630
Total	684	100.0	167	100.0	851

Polissya (Kolomiychuk et al. 2024b). For instance, Biloozerskyi contains 2 species of lycophytes, compared to 3 in Zalissia; 6 species of horsetails, compared to 5 in

Zalissia; 14 species of ferns, compared to 12 in Zalissia; and two native gymnosperm species in each park. In local floras of the forest-steppe zone, such high numbers of these vascular plant groups are rare. However, comparable richness has been documented in certain other areas associated with the Dnipro River basin, such as Kaniv Nature Reserve in Cherkasy Oblast (Shevchyk et al. 1996), Pyriatynskyi National Nature Park in Poltava Oblast (Kovalenko 2016) and even within the steppe zone of Dnipropetrovsk Oblast (Baranovskyi et al. 2017).

The total flora diversity includes 684 native plants from 328 genera in 84 families and 167 alien plants from 124 genera in 47 families. The level of adventitization of the studied flora is 19.56 %, which is consistent with other major protected areas in lowland Ukraine, where the average proportion of adventive species is reported at 16 % (Burda et al. 2015). This suggests a relatively well-preserved native floristic core, which acts as a barrier against the active spread of alien plant species. Due to adventitization, the studied flora includes the representatives from 76 new genera and 12 new families, especially Acoraceae, Asphodelaceae, Cucurbitaceae, Elaeagnaceae, Juglandaceae, Moraceae, Nyctaginaceae, Oxalidaceae, Portulacaceae, Rutaceae, Verbenaceae and Vitaceae. Among the alien species, 71 are ergasiophygophytes (including several ergasio-xenophytes that first naturalized in Ukraine from cultivation but subsequently spread as xenophytes, such as *Ambrosia artemisiifolia* L. and *Geranium sibiricum* L.), whereas 96 species are xenophytes.

Among the major families, Asteraceae and Poaceae are the most species-rich, which is typical for regional floras of the Palearctic. The third-ranking family is Cyperaceae, which is diversest in boreal regions. This type of leading triad of plant families is characteristic of floras in the northern regions of Eurasia (Khokhryakov 2000). The Rosaceae family holds a prominent position as well, which aligns with floras of Central Europe. The top five dominant families of the native flora fraction are identical to those of the Eastern Polissia region (Lukash 2009).

Additionally, the native fraction of the flora includes other well-represented families, which are typically diverse in temperate or southern Eurasian regions: Fabaceae (31 species), Apiaceae (26 species), Brassicaceae (20 species) and Ranunculaceae (20 species). Despite minor differences in ranking, the top ten families of the native fraction are similar in Bilozerskyi, Zalissia and Pyriatynskyi National Nature Parks, indicating common florogenetic processes among these closely located areas.

The distribution of dominant families in the adventive fraction of the Park's flora follows trends typical for adventive and synanthropic floras across Ukraine (Protopopova 1991). The top three families are dominated by taxa with a high proportion of short-lived species, predominantly of Mediterranean or North American origin (Tab. 3).

Among the largest genera of the flora, the boreal genus *Carex* is the absolute leader, with 35 native species (5.1 % of the native flora). Other large genera include: *Veronica* – 14 (11 native), *Trifolium* – 12 (10 native), *Pilosella* – 10 native, *Ranunculus*

Tab. 3 Major families of the flora of Biloozerskyi National Nature Park.

Native plants			Alien plants		
№	Family	Number of taxa	№	Family	Number of taxa
1	Asteraceae	81	1	Asteraceae	31
2	Poaceae	57	2	Poaceae	21
3	Cyperaceae	44	3	Brassicaceae	14
4	Rosaceae	37	4	Fabaceae	11
5	Lamiaceae	34	5	Rosaceae	10
6	Caryophyllaceae	33	6	Amaranthaceae	6

Tab. 4 Geographical structure of the native plants of the flora of Biloozerskyi National Nature Park.

Geographical elements	Number of taxa	%
Eurasian	167	24.5
European	123	17.8
Euro-Mediterranean	90	13.4
Palaearctic	80	11.7
Holarctic	59	8.6
Boreal	58	8.6
Multiregional	26	3.8
Mediterranean	24	3.5
Eurasian Steppe	22	3.2
Eurasian North-Steppe	18	2.6
Euro-Siberian	16	2.3
Total	684	100.0

Tab. 5 Geographical structure of the alien plants of the Biloozerskyi National Nature Park flora.

Origin	Number of taxa	%
Mediterranean*	78	46.7
American	39	23.4
Asian	32	19.2
European	9	5.4
Anthropogenic	6	3.6
Eurasian	3	1.8
Total	167	100.0

Tab. 6 Biomorphological structure of the flora of the Biloozerskyi National Nature Park.

Life forms	Native plants		Alien plants	
	Number of taxa	%	Number of taxa	%
Trees	31	4.5	19	11.4
Shrubs	30	4.5	13	7.7
Subshrubs	10	1.5	-	-
Lianas	1	0.1	2	1.2
Perennials	446	65.2	30	18.0
Short-lived, biennials and annuals	130	19.0	101	60.5
Aquatics	36	5.3	2	1.2
Total	684	100	167	100

and *Rumex* – 9 each (8 native), *Prunus* – 10 (5 native), *Potentilla* – 9 native, *Bromus* – 9 (4 native), *Poa* – 8 native, *Salix* – 8 (7 native), *Campanula* and *Silene* – 8 native each. However, several typically species-rich genera in the forest-steppe zone – such as *Astragalus*, *Centaurea*, *Euphorbia*, *Galium*, *Rosa*, *Vicia* and *Viola* – are represented in the Park’s flora by fewer species than is usual for typical forest-steppe floras. This may be due to the specific phytocoenotic conditions of Biloozerskyi and the incomplete representation of certain forest-steppe biotopes.

The geographical structure of the studied flora is highly diverse (Tab. 4). Broadly distributed geoelements (Eurasian, Holarctic, Palearctic and multiregional) collectively account for 48.6 % of the total flora (320 species) (Fig. 2). Among the zonal geoelements, European and Euro-Mediterranean elements predominate, with a relatively high proportion of boreal species – an unusual feature for the Forest-Steppe zone. When the zonal geoelements are grouped into two major categories – "northern type" (boreal, European and Euro-Siberian elements) and "southern type" (Mediterranean, Eurasian North-Steppe, Eurasian Steppe and Euro-Mediterranean elements), the northern group (28.7 %) exceeds the southern group (22.7 %). This highlights the geographical similarity of the studied flora to those of other local floras in Polissia (Bezsmertna et al. 2024; Kolomyichuk et al. 2024b).

The alien plants of the Park are dominated by species of “southern” origin, originating from the regions of Mediterranean and Asia, together comprising 65.9 % of all alien plants (Tab. 5). This trend is generally characteristic of alien plant checklists across Ukraine (Zajac 1979; Protopopova 1991). In recent years, the Middle Dnipro region has continued to experience the active spread of new alien species from arid and warmer regions, driven by global climate change (Didukh 2023; Koniakin et al. 2024). At the same time, a high proportion of adventive species of American origin is also evident, a trend that is common in many European floras (Burda & Tokhtar 1998).

Fig. 2 Distribution of geographical elements of native plants of the flora of the Biloozerskyi National Nature Park. Main geographical element groups: A – broadly distributed plants; B – "northern type"; C – "southern type".

Tab. 7 Ecologically and biomorphologically structure of the flora of the Biloozerskyi National Nature Park (according to: Raunkiaer 1907).

Life forms	Native plants		Alien plants	
	Number of taxa	%	Number of taxa	%
Phanerophytes	55	8.2	33	19.7
Chamaephytes	22	3.2	3	1.8
Hemicryptophytes	421	61.5	40	24.0
Cryptophytes	74	10.8	7	4.2
Therophytes	76	11.1	82	49.1
Hydrophytes	36	5.3	2	1.2
Total	684	100	167	100

Tab. 8 General distribution of native species among main biotope groups (coenofloras) of the flora of the Biloozerskyi National Nature Park.

Biotope groups	Number of taxa	%
V – Light, fresh, and moist pine and mixed (oak-pine) forests	300	43.9
VII – Fresh and moist meadows, forest edges	273	39.9
VI – Meadow steppes and derived shrublands and woodlands	270	39.5
II – Eutrophic wetlands and riparian vegetation	156	22.7
IX – Synantropic biotopes	143	20.9
IV – Fresh shady oak forests	141	20.6
VIII – Dry pine woodlands and open sandy areas	111	16.2
III – Oligo-mesotrophic sedge, shrub, and forested bogs	84	12.4
I – Eutrophic and mesotrophic water bodies	39	5.7
Total native plants	684	100

Regarding the time of introduction, the adventive fraction of the Park's flora consists of 67 archaeophytes (40.1 %) and 100 neophytes (59.9 %). This ratio is similar to that observed in the flora of Zalissia National Nature Park (Kolomyichuk et al. 2024b), indicating comparable patterns in the formation of alien plants in both floras.

The natural biomorphological structure of the Park's flora was formed under the influence of the temperate continental climate in a forested area. The dominance of perennials among native species is characteristic of most natural floras in Ukraine. The proportion of woody plants in the life-form spectrum is 10.5 %, which is average for the Middle Dnipro region and the forest-steppe zone in general. For comparison, the proportion of woody plants in different floras is as follows: Zalissia National Nature Park (border of Polissia and Forest-Steppe) – 11.6 % (Kolomyichuk et al. 2024b), regional flora of Eastern Polissia – 12.02 % (Lukash 2009), regional flora of Kyiv Polissia – 7.2 % (Mosyakin 1990), natural flora of Kyiv City – 9.51 % (Grechyshkina 2010), regional flora of Rzhyschchiv united territorial community, Kyiv Oblast – 9.4 % (Shynder et al. 2021).

According to Raunkiaer's (1907) classification, hemicryptophytes predominate among native plants, where as therophytes dominate the alien plants. This pattern is typical for most floras across Ukraine (Protopopova 1991).

The significantly higher proportion of woody plants in the adventive fraction (trees, shrubs and lianas together make up 20.3 %) compared with the native fraction is due

to the extensive use of alien trees and shrubs in forestry practices. Many of these plants have naturalized and even become invasive, such as *Acer negundo* L., *Morus alba* L., *Prunus cerasifera* Ehrh., *P. serotina* Ehrh. and *Robinia pseudoacacia* L.

Ecological-Phytocoenotic analysis

The general spectrum of habitat representativeness (Tab. 8) indicates that the highest number of native plant species is found in light, fresh, and moist pine forests. Meadow steppes with derived shrublands, as well as meadows and forest edges, also show high species richness. Each of these three habitat groups contains over 40 % of the native plants diversity (Fig. 3). At the same time, forest habitats together (pine ecosystems and oak forests, groups IV and V) contain only 321 species (46.9 %), accounting for just under half of the native plants. Wetland and psammophytic (sandy) habitats have lower species richness but still exhibit relatively high diversity. Overall, the ecological-phytocoenotic structure of the flora reflects the organic integration of forest and forest-steppe biotopes, reinforcing the intrazonal nature of the studied flora.

The various coenofloras of the Park exhibit distinct geographical patterns due to differences in their florogenetic origins (Tab. 9). In the aquatic coenoflora (group I), species with broad distributions dominate (75.6 %), with multiregional elements being the most common. This characteristic is expected, as the buffering properties of aquatic environments mitigate geographic factors such as continentality and temperature. A total of 29 species (70.7 %) in the aquatic coenoflora are specific to these biotopes (i.e., they do not occur in other habitat types in the Park). Two alien species (*Elodea canadensis* Michx. and *E. nuttallii*) are present in this coenofloras.

Fig. 3 Species richness of main biotope groups (coenofloras) in the territory of Bilozerskyi National Nature Park (biotope groups I–IX are given in the Methodology and Tab. 8).

Tab. 9 Distribution of geographical elements within coenofloras.

Geographical elements	Coenofloras								
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX
Eurasian	7	45	24	35	79	82	79	24	52
Palaearctic	5	25	8	18	41	37	47	13	27
Holarctic	7	25	15	6	16	12	25	5	10
Multiregional	12	5	1	4	3	1	2	1	6
European	6	21	10	32	55	43	40	25	16
Boreal	2	13	21	5	31	9	15	6	1
Euro-Siberian	0	3	2	3	8	5	10	0	0
Euro-Mediterranean	0	15	1	34	48	41	41	14	22
Eurasian Steppe	0	1	0	0	2	12	4	11	2
Mediterranean	0	0	0	3	6	13	3	7	4
Eurasian North-Steppe	0	1	0	1	11	14	5	4	2
Total native plants	39	154	82	141	300	269	271	110	142
Alien plants	2	17	3	20	32	30	51	11	43
Total	41	171	85	161	332	299	322	121	185

A similar biogeographic pattern and ecological determinants were observed in the eutrophic wetland coenoflora (group II), where 58.2 % of species have broad distributions. A notable feature of this coenoflora is its higher level of adventization (10.0 %), indicating the impact of invasive species. The group of 42 specific species (24.7 % of the coenoflora) is highly diverse in terms of geoelements, such as *Carex elongata* L. (European geographical element), *Onoclea struthiopteris* (boreal) and *Ribes nigrum* L. (Eurasian).

The coenoflora of the mesotrophic bogs (group III) is characterized by a significant presence of Eurasian (27.9 %) and boreal (25.6 %) geoelements, which together with broadly distributed species constitute 81.4 % of its composition. The overall structure of geoelements in bog coenofloras has been shaped by their development history. Pleistocene cooling prevented the restoration of thermophilic wetland vegetation in temperate regions of Europe and contributed to the formation of a new composition of wetland flora (Bogdanovskaya-Gienef 1946). Among the 19 specific marsh plants (22.1 %), boreal geoelements predominate, including *Drosera rotundifolia* L., *Menyanthes trifoliata* L., *Pedicularis palustris* L. and *Ranunculus flammula* L. The level of adventization in the mesotrophic bog coenoflora is quite low (3.5 %), which can be explained by the specificity of these habitats and their resistance to the invasion of neophytes.

The coenoflora of fresh shady oak forests on rich soils (IV) is relatively species-poor within the territory of the Park, which aligns with the general trend of decreasing species diversity in Eurasian broadleaved forests from west to east (Kleopov 1990). However, on the opposite right bank of the Dnipro River, there is a noticeable greater species diversity of this coenoflora, by several dozen species. For example, in hornbeam-oak forest of Kaniv Nature Reserve, located 12 km from the Park, 189 vascular plant species were recorded (Shevchyk 2005). In total, 304 plant species have been reported for broadleaved forests along the right bank of the Dnipro River (Lyubchenko 1986). Notably, nearly half of the coenoflora's composition consists of

European and Euro-Mediterranean species (41.0 %), which is close to the proportion found in the broadleaved forests of Eastern Europe (46 %) (Kleopov 1990). Among the 22 specific species (13.7 %), Euro-Mediterranean elements predominate, including *Acer campestre* L., *Campanula trachelium* L. and *Prunus avium* (L.) L. The relatively high level of adventitization (12.4 %) is likely due to both structural disturbances in these forests resulting from their past exploitation and the significant floristic incompleteness of certain layers due to the historical youth of these communities in the Park.

The combined coenoflora of pine and mixed (oak-pine) forests (V) is the richest in the Park, primarily due to the weakened edificatory influence of adult trees on the understory and the herb layer in these edapho-hydrological conditions. This coenoflora includes all geoelements, with a predominance of broadly distributed species (41.9 %), as well as significant shares of European and Euro-Mediterranean (31.0 % together) and boreal (9.3 %) geoelements. Among the 31 specific species (9.3 %), boreal (*Equisetum sylvaticum* L., *Lycopodium annotinum*, *L. clavatum* L., *Rubus saxatilis* L.) and European and Euro-Mediterranean (*Carex brizoides* L., *Platanthera chlorantha* (Custer) Rchb., *Serratula tinctoria* L., *Silphiodaucus prutenicus* (L.) Spalik, Wojew., Banasiak, Piwczyński & Reduron, *Tanacetum corymbosum* (L.) Sch.Bip., *Thesium ebracteatum*) plants predominate. The relatively low adventitization level (9.5 %) indicates the resistance of these biotopes to the neophyte invasion.

Despite the limited representation of meadow steppes on loess slopes and derived communities (VI), their coenoflora exhibits considerable floristic richness. This coenoflora is dominated by broadly distributed (44.2 %) and European and Euro-Mediterranean (28.1 % together) geoelements. The coenoflora contains 41 specific species (13.7 %), among which the Eurasian steppe and Mediterranean geoelements predominate. But, this biotope group has weak representation in the Park, and its species composition poorly reflects the regional characteristics of the Left-Bank Forest-Steppe, where the proportion of steppe geoelements in the flora as a whole reaches 25.2 % (Smolyar 2000). The relatively low level of adventitization (10.0 %) indicates the resistance of these habitats to the neophyte invasion.

The biotope group of fresh and moist meadows, forest edges, and woodlands on moderately rich soils (VII) is represented by small and fragmented patches within the forested area of the Park, yet it supports a relatively rich coenoflora. Similar to other coenofloras in the Park, it is compound by broadly distributed species (47.5 %), with a significant proportion of European and Euro-Mediterranean (25.2 % together) geoelements. A distinctive feature of the geographical structure of this coenoflora compared to others in the Park is the strong representation of Euro-Siberian species (*Iris sibirica* L., *Silene noctiflora* L., *Succisa pratensis* Moench, *Gratiola officinalis* L.). The increased adventitization level (15.8 %) is generally typical for meadow coenoses due to their high instability and susceptibility to various dynamic processes, including degradation-regeneration cycles, fluctuations and other ecological disturbances.

Dry pine woodlands and open sandy areas (VIII) cover relatively large areas in the Park and have a highly specific coenoflora. In terms of light requirements and

drought tolerance, the species of this coenoflora resemble those of meadow steppes, yet they are distinctly different due to their psammophytic and oligotrophic nature. In addition to broadly distributed species (35.5 %), the coenoflora is significantly influenced by European and Euro-Mediterranean (32.2 % together) and "southern" (18.2 % together) geoelements. 33 specific species (27.3 %) are obligate psammophytes from various geoelements, such as *Carex colchica* J.Gay, *Koeleria glauca* (Spreng.) DC., *Secale sylvestre* Host and *Stipa borysthena* Klokov ex Prokudin. This coenoflora shows a moderate level of adventitization (9.1 %).

Synanthropic biotopes in the Park are relatively limited in area and fragmented, concentrated along the transport network, recreational and managed areas. However, the synanthropic coenoflora is quite diverse and consists mainly of anthropotolerant native plants. The share of alien plants, i.e. the level of adventitization of this coenoflora, is the highest among all coenofloras (23.2 %).

Rare plants

During the study of the Park's territory, 107 (15.6 %) native plants with current protected status were recorded. Of these, 25 species are included in the Red Data Book of Ukraine (Order 111), nine – in the Revised Annex to the Bern Convention (Bern Convention 2011), four of them are also listed in the Red Data Book of Ukraine and eleven species are listed in the Red List of Europe (Bilz et al. 2011) in threat categories which is higher than LC, three of them are also listed in the Red Data Book of Ukraine. Additionally, 71 species are recommended for protection within Kyiv and Cherkasy oblasts. Many rare plants in the territory of the Bilozerskyi Park are endangered in the Forest-Steppe zone and are situated at the southern limit of their distribution. This is especially true of the boreal and Eurosiberian geoelements. Based on the number of this taxa, the coenofloras of the designated biotope groups are ranked as follows: 1) Group V – 42 rare plants; 2) Group VI – 20 rare plants; 3) Group IV – 18 rare plants; 4) Group III – 16 rare plants; 5) Group VIII – 15 rare plants; 6) Group I – 9 rare plants; 7) Group II – 9 rare plants; and 8) Group VII – 6 rare plants. Thus, all groups of natural biotopes are habitats of rare plants, but forest and wetland habitats stand out in particular. This confirms the high level of ecological and coenotic diversity of the studied flora and its status as a center of representativeness of rare plants in the Middle Dnipro region of Ukraine.

Invasive plants

Despite the relatively preserved natural core of flora, 35 alien invasive plants, which are common in the flora of Ukraine (Protopopova & Shevera 2019), have been registered in the Park. However, the degree of threat posed by these species varies. For example, 13 annuals and biennials (such as *Ambrosia artemisiifolia*, *Erigeron canadensis* L., *Xanthium orientale* L.) from this list spread in synanthropic habitats and show no tendency to establish themselves in natural phytocoenoses. On the other hand, alien therophytes such as *Bidens frondosa* L., *Echinocystis lobata* (Michx.) Torr. & A.Gray, *Impatiens parviflora* DC. and *Senecio viscosus* L., along with

the hydrophyte *Elodea canadensis*, do establish themselves in natural biotopes and thus pose a competitive threat to native species. Seven invasive perennials, due to their higher phytocoenotic positions and competitive ability, pose even greater threats to local plants, with *Asclepias syriaca* L. and *Solidago canadensis* L. being particularly dangerous. Even more threatening are woody plants, as they can dominate the upper layers of vegetation and suppress the herbaceous layer. This group includes two alien shrubs (*Amelanchier xspicata* (Lam.) K.Koch and *Amorpha fruticosa* L.), one liana (*Parthenocissus inserta* (A.Kern.) Fritsch), and six trees (*Acer negundo*, *Elaeagnus angustifolia* L., *Prunus serotina*, *Quercus rubra* L., *Robinia pseudoacacia*, and *Salix xfragilis* L.). Several alien species are potentially invasive. They have been found in the Park at early stages of spread and thus require further monitoring, including *Phragmites australis* subsp. *isiacus* (Arcang.) J.H.Xue, Chepinoga & K.P.Ma, *Populus xcanadensis* Moench and *Zizania latifolia* (Griseb.) Hance ex F.Muell.

One of the sources of diversity and spread of alien plants is two landfills near the Park's boundaries, where many xenophytes and ergasiophygophytes have been found, which were not observed elsewhere in the studied areas. These landfills have specific features that allow exotic plants to survive: water accumulation, increased soil nutrient content due to organic waste decomposition, and the thermohydrological characteristics of the substrate, as the waste layer acts as mulch. These factors enable many otherwise unstable alien plants to thrive, bloom, and even fruit, thus undergoing acclimatization. Thus, landfills serve as initial habitats in the naturalization process of alien plants, making their proximity to the Park an additional factor contributing to the potential invasion of new invasive plants. Among the spontaneously growing species recorded, the greatest threats are posed by perennials *Phytolacca acinosa* Roxb. and *Thladiantha dubia* Bunge, which require monitoring (Kostruba et al. 2021).

Conclusions

Thus, it has been established that the flora of Biloozerskyi National Nature Park comprises 851 taxa of vascular plants, representing about 42.4 % of the regional flora of the Middle Dnipro region. There are 684 species of native plants, while there are 167 alien species with an adventization coefficient of 19.6 %. The flora is dominated by broadly distributed geoelements (48.6 %), as well as European (17.8 %) and Euro-Mediterranean (13.4 %), emphasizing the forested nature of the studied area, which represents an intrazonal "island" within the Forest-Steppe zone. The majority of alien plants (46.7 %) has Mediterranean origins. In the biomorphological structure, perennials (65.2 %) and hemicryptophytes (61.5 %) dominate within native plants, while the proportion of woody biomorphs (10.5 %) is typical for this region. The ecological-phytocoenotic analysis revealed high species representativeness in pine and oak-pine forests (43.9 %), meadow (39.9 %), and meadow-steppe (and derived from them) (39.5 %) biotopes, while the oak forest coenoflora (20.6 %) is relatively species-poor. The high proportion of rare plants (15.6 %) underscores the Park's

crucial role in conserving vascular plant diversity in the central part of Ukraine. Biloozerskyi National Nature Park is a key biodiversity hotspot in the Middle Dnipro region and requires further research and conservation measures to protect its unique natural complexes.

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Appendix

Annotated checklist of vascular plants of Bilozerskyi National Nature Park

Abbreviations: Erg – ergasiophygyte, Xen – xenophyte, Erg.-Xen. – ergasio-xenophyte, L. f. – life form.

Range (for native) and origin (for alien): Am – American, As – Asian, Bor – Boreal, Euras – Eurasian, Euro – European, Euro-Med – Euro-Mediterranean, Euro-Sib – Euro-Siberian, N. Steppe – Eurasian North-Steppe, Hol – Holarctic, Med – Mediterranean (or Sub-Mediterranean), Multi – Multiregional, PArct – Palearctic, Steppe – Eurasian Steppe, anthrop – anthropogenic

Coen. – coenoflora groups (number – described in the Methodology).

Dist. – distribution in administrative regions: Kv – Kyiv Oblast, Crk – Cherkasy Oblast

Unnumbered in the Checklist are certain varieties and forms, as well as species that had been cited previously but could not be confirmed during the present floristic survey. Records considered unlikely or clearly erroneous are provided in separate notes.

LYCOPHYTES

Lycopodiidae

Lycopodiaceae

1. *Lycopodium annotinum* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv
2. *Lycopodium clavatum* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

FERNS

Equisetidae

Equisetaceae

3. *Equisetum arvense* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
4. *Equisetum fluviatile* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 2,3. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
5. *Equisetum hyemale* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Multi. – Coen.: 4,5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
6. *Equisetum palustre* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 2,3,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
7. *Equisetum pratense* Ehrh.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 5,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
8. *Equisetum sylvaticum* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Ophioglossidae

Ophioglossaceae

9. *Botrychium matricariifolium* (Retz.) A.Braun ex W.D.J.Koch: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv
10. *Ophioglossum vulgatum* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv

Polypodiidae

Athyriaceae

11. *Athyrium filix-femina* (L.) Roth: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Multi. – Coen.: 4,5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Cystopteridaceae

12. *Cystopteris fragilis* (L.) Bernh.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Multi. – Coen.: 4. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
13. *Gymnocarpium dryopteris* (L.) Newman: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Dryopteridaceae

14. *Dryopteris carthusiana* (Vill.) H.P.Fuchs: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 3,4,5,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
15. *Dryopteris cristata* (L.) A.Gray: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 3,5. – Dist.: Kv
16. *Dryopteris filix-mas* (L.) Schott: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 2,4,5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
17. *Polystichum aculeatum* (L.) Roth: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 4. – Dist.: Crk

Onocleaceae

18. *Onoclea struthiopteris* (L.) Roth: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv

Polypodiaceae

19. *Polypodium vulgare* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Multi. – Coen.: 4,5,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Pteridiaceae

20. *Pteridium pinetorum* C.N.Page & R.R.Mill: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Salviniaceae

21. *Salvinia natans* (L.) All.: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 1. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Thelypteridaceae

22. *Thelypteris palustris* Schott: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 2,3. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

GYMNOSPERMAE

Pinidae

Cupressaceae

23. *Juniperus communis* L.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 5,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Pinaceae

24. *Picea abies* (L.) H.Karst.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: tree. – Origin: Bor. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

25. *Pinus sylvestris* L.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 3,5,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

ANGIOSPERMAE

Basal angiosperms

Nymphaeaceae

26. *Nuphar lutea* (L.) Sm.: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 1. – Dist.: Kv

27. *Nymphaea alba* L.: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 1. – Dist.: Kv

28. *Nymphaea candida* C.Presl: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: Euro. – Dist.: Kv

Clade magnoliids

Aristolochiaceae

29. *Aristolochia clematitis* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

30. *Asarum europaeum* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 4. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Clade monocots

Acoraceae

31. *Acorus calamus* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: perennial. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv

Alismataceae

32. *Alisma lanceolatum* With.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv

33. *Alisma plantago-aquatica* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

34. *Sagittaria sagittifolia* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 1,2. – Dist.: Kv

Amaryllidaceae

35. *Allium oleraceum* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

36. *Allium paniculatum* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: N. Steppe. – Coen.: 5,6. – Dist.: Kv

37. *Allium scorodoprasum* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

38. *Allium sphaerocephalon* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Med. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv

Araceae

39. *Calla palustris* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv

40. *Lemna gibba* L.: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: Multi. – Coen.: 1. – Dist.: Kv

41. *Lemna minor* L.: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: Multi. – Coen.: 1. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

42. *Lemna trisulca* L.: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: Multi. – Coen.: 1. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

43. *Spirodela polyrhiza* (L.) Schleid.: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: Multi. – Coen.: 1. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

44. *Wolffia arrhiza* (L.) Horkel ex Wimm.: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 1. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Asparagaceae

45. *Anthericum ramosum* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5,6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

46. *Asparagus officinalis* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

47. *Convallaria majalis* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 4,5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

48. *Maianthemum bifolium* (L.) F.W.Schmidt: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.:

- Kv, Crk
49. *Polygonatum multiflorum* (L.) All.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 4. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
50. *Polygonatum odoratum* (Mill.) Druce: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,4. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
51. *Scilla bifolia* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 4. – Dist.: Kv
- Asphodeliaceae**
52. *Hemerocallis fulva* (L.) L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: perennial. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
- Butomaceae**
53. *Butomus umbellatus* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
- Cyperaceae**
54. *Bolboschoenus maritimus* (L.) Palla: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol (cited after Rogowicz 1869; Yarova 2015)
55. *Carex acuta* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 2,3. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
56. *Carex acutiformis* Ehrh.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,3. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
57. *Carex appropinquata* Schumach.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 2,3. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
58. *Carex brizoides* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv
59. *Carex caryophyllea* Latourr.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
60. *Carex cespitosa* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,3. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
61. *Carex colchica* J.Gay: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
62. *Carex diandra* Schrank: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 3. – Dist.: Kv
63. *Carex digitata* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 4,5,6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
64. *Carex distans* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv
65. *Carex disticha* Huds.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Sib. – Coen.: 2,3. – Dist.: Kv
66. *Carex divulsa* Stokes: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 5,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
67. *Carex elata* All.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv
68. *Carex elongata* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
69. *Carex ericetorum* Pollich: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 5,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
70. *Carex hartmaniorum* A.Cajander: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 3. – Dist.: Kv
71. *Carex hirta* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 2,5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
72. *Carex humilis* Leyss.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv
73. *Carex lasiocarpa* Ehrh.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 3. – Dist.: Kv
74. *Carex leporina* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
75. *Carex michelii* Host: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Med. – Coen.: 4,5,6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
76. *Carex montana* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5,6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
77. *Carex muricata* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
78. *Carex nigra* (L.) Reichard: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
79. *Carex otrubae* Podp.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
80. *Carex pallescens* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 5,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
81. *Carex pilosa* Scop.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 4. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
82. *Carex praecox* Schreb.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,7,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
83. *Carex pseudocyperus* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 2,3. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
84. *Carex remota* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
85. *Carex riparia* Curtis: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
86. *Carex rostrata* Stokes: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 3. – Dist.: Kv
87. *Carex spicata* Huds.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
88. *Carex sylvatica* Huds.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 4,5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
89. *Carex vulpina* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
90. *Cyperus fuscus* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
91. *Eleocharis acicularis* (L.) Roem. & Schult.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
92. *Eleocharis palustris* (L.) Roem. & Schult.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

93. *Eriophorum angustifolium* Honck.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 3. – Dist.: Kv
 94. *Eriophorum gracile* W.D.J.Koch: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 3. – Dist.: Kv
 95. *Schoenoplectus lacustris* (L.) Palla: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 96. *Scirpoides holoschoenus* (L.) Soják: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Med (cited after Yarova 2015)
 97. *Scirpus sylvaticus* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Hydrocharitaceae

98. *Elodea canadensis* Michx.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: aquatic. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 1. – Dist.: Kv
 99. *Elodea nuttallii* (Planch.) H.St.John: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: aquatic. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 1. – Dist.: Kv
 100. *Hydrocharis morsus-ranae* L.: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 1. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 101. *Najas marina* L.: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: Multi. – Coen.: 1. – Dist.: Kv
 102. *Stratiotes aloides* L.: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 1. – Dist.: Kv

Iridaceae

103. *Gladiolus imbricatus* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 6,7. – Dist.: Kv
 104. *Iris aphylla* L. var. *hungarica* (Waldst. & Kit.) D.Dubovik: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Med. – Coen.: 5,6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 105. *Iris arenaria* Waldst. & Kit.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: N. Steppe. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv
 106. *Iris pseudacorus* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 107. *Iris sibirica* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Sib. – Coen.: 6,7. – Dist.: Kv

Juncaceae

108. *Juncus articulatus* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 2,3,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 109. *Juncus bufonius* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Multi. – Coen.: 2,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 110. *Juncus compressus* Jacq.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 111. *Juncus conglomeratus* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 3,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 112. *Juncus effusus* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 3,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 113. *Juncus inflexus* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv
 114. *Juncus tenuis* Willd.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: perennial. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 115. *Luzula campestris* (L.) DC.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 116. *Luzula multiflora* (Ehrh.) Lej.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 117. *Luzula pallescens* Sw.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 Note. *Luzula divulgata* Kirschner was also cited (Yarova 2015), but the occurrence of this species requires confirmation.

Juncaginaceae

Note. The record of *Triglochin maritima* L. from a salt marsh near Khotsky village (Rogowicz 1869; Yarova 2015) probably does not concern the present territory of the Park

Liliaceae

118. *Fritillaria ruthenica* Wikstr.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv
 119. *Gagea fragifera* (Vill.) E.Bayer & G.López: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 4,5,6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 120. *Gagea lutea* (L.) Ker Gawl.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 4. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 121. *Gagea minima* (L.) Ker Gawl.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 4. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 122. *Lilium martagon* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Sib. – Coen.: 4,5. – Dist.: Kv

Melanthiaceae

123. *Paris quadrifolia* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 4. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 124. *Veratrum nigrum* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv

Orchidaceae

125. *Dactylorhiza incarnata* (L.) Soó: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras(w). – Coen.: 3. – Dist.: Kv
 126. *Epipactis helleborine* (L.) Crantz: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 4,5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 127. *Epipactis palustris* (L.) Crantz: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,3. – Dist.: Kv
 128. *Liparis loeselii* (L.) Rich.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 2,3. – Dist.: Kv

129. *Neottia nidus-avis* (L.) Rich.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PARct. – Dist.: Kv
 130. *Platanthera bifolia* (L.) Rich.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 4,5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 131. *Platanthera chlorantha* (Custer) Rchb.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv

Poaceae

132. *Agropyron cristatum* (L.) Gaertn. var. *pectinatum* (M.Bieb.) B.Fedtsch.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Med. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv
 133. *Agrostis capillaris* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 134. *Agrostis gigantea* Roth: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 135. *Agrostis stolonifera* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 2,3. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 136. *Agrostis vinealis* Schreb.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 5,6,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 137. *Alopecurus aequalis* Sobol.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv
 138. *Alopecurus arundinaceus* Poir.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv
 139. *Alopecurus geniculatus* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv
 140. *Alopecurus pratensis* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 141. *Anthoxanthum repens* (Host) Veldkamp: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: N. Steppe. – Coen.: 5,6,7,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 142. *Anthoxanthum odoratum* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 5,6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 143. *Apera spica-venti* (L.) P.Beauv.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv
 144. *Arrhenatherum elatius* (L.) P.Beauv. ex J.Presl & C.Presl: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: perennial. – Origin: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 145. *Avena fatua* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv
 146. *Avenula pubescens* (Huds.) Dumort.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 147. *Brachypodium pinnatum* (L.) P.Beauv.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 148. *Brachypodium sylvaticum* (Huds.) P.Beauv.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 4,5,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 149. *Briza media* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv
 150. *Bromus arvensis* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 151. *Bromus benekenii* (Lange) Trimen: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 4. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 152. *Bromus commutatus* Schrad.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 153. *Bromus hordeaceus* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 154. *Bromus inermis* Leyss.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 155. *Bromus japonicus* Hoult.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 156. *Bromus squarrosus* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 157. *Bromus sterilis* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 158. *Bromus tectorum* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 159. *Calamagrostis arundinacea* (L.) Roth: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 5,6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 160. *Calamagrostis canescens* (Weber) Roth: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 3. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 161. *Calamagrostis epigejos* (L.) Roth: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,7,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 162. *Calamagrostis stricta* (Timm) Koeler: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 3. – Dist.: Kv
 163. *Corynephorus canescens* (L.) P.Beauv.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv
 164. *Dactylis glomerata* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 165. *Deschampsia cespitosa* (L.) P.Beauv.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 2,5,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 166. *Digitaria ischaemum* (Schreb.) Muhl.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Euro. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

167. *Digitaria sanguinalis* (L.) Scop.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
168. *Echinochloa crus-galli* (L.) P.Beauv.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
169. *Elymus repens* (L.) Gould: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
170. *Eragrostis minor* Host: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
171. *Eragrostis pilosa* (L.) P.Beauv.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
172. *Eriochloa villosa* (Thunb.) Kunth: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv
173. *Festuca beckeri* (Hack.) Trautv.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Steppe. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
174. *Festuca rubra* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
175. *Festuca rupicola* Heuff.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Steppe. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
176. *Glyceria fluitans* (L.) R.Br.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
177. *Hordeum vulgare* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv
178. *Glyceria maxima* (Hartm.) Holmb.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
179. *Koeleria glauca* (Spreng.) DC.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
180. *Koeleria macrantha* (Ledeb.) Schult.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv
181. *Leersia oryzoides* (L.) Sw.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 2,7. – Dist.: Kv
182. *Lolium arundinaceum* (Schreb.) Darbysh. subsp. *orientale* (Hack.) G.H.Loos: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Med. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
183. *Lolium giganteum* (L.) Darbysh.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 4,5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
184. *Lolium perenne* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
185. *Lolium pratense* (Huds.) Darbysh.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
186. *Melica nutans* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 4,5,6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
187. *Milium effusum* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 4,5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
188. *Molinia caerulea* (L.) Moench: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 5,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
189. *Phleum phleoides* (L.) H.Karst.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 6,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
190. *Phleum pratense* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 5,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
191. *Phragmites australis* (Cav.) Trin. ex Steud. subsp. *australis*: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Multi. – Coen.: 2,3. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
192. *Phragmites australis* subsp. *isiacus* (Arcang.) J.H.Xue, Chepinoga & K.P.Ma (= *P. altissimus* (Benth.) Mabile): Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: perennial. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
193. *Poa angustifolia* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 5,6,7,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
194. *Poa annua* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Multi. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
195. *Poa bulbosa* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Med. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
196. *Poa compressa* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 5,6,7,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
197. *Poa nemoralis* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 4,5,6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
198. *Poa palustris* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 2,3. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
199. *Poa pratensis* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
200. *Poa trivialis* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 4,5,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
201. *Secale sylvestre* Host: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Steppe. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
202. *Setaria pumila* (Poir.) Roem. & Schult.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
203. *Setaria verticillata* (L.) P.Beauv.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
204. *Setaria viridis* (L.) P.Beauv.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
205. *Stipa borysthenica* Klokov ex Prokudin: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: N. Steppe. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
206. *Stipa capillata* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Steppe. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv
Stipa pennata L.: listed according to (Yarova 2015)
207. *Thinopyrum intermedium* (Host) Barkworth & D.R.Dewey: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-

- Med. – Coen.: 6,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 208. *Triticum aestivum* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 209. *Zizania latifolia* (Griseb.) Hance ex F.Muell.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: perennial. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Note. *Cynodon dactylon* (L.) Pers. was also cited (Yarova 2015), but the occurrence of this species requires confirmation.

Potamogetonaceae

210. *Potamogeton acutifolius* Link: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 1. – Dist.: Kv
 211. *Potamogeton crispus* L.: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: Multi. – Coen.: 1. – Dist.: Kv
 212. *Potamogeton gramineus* L.: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 1. – Dist.: Kv
 213. *Potamogeton lucens* L.: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 1. – Dist.: Kv
 214. *Potamogeton natans* L.: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 1. – Dist.: Kv
 215. *Potamogeton nodosus* Poir.: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: Multi. – Coen.: 1. – Dist.: Kv
 216. *Potamogeton perfoliatus* L.: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: Multi. – Coen.: 1. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 217. *Stuckenia pectinata* (L.) Börner: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: Multi. – Coen.: 1. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Typhaceae

218. *Sparganium emersum* Rehmann: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 1,2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 219. *Sparganium erectum* L.: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 1,2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 220. *Sparganium natans* L.: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 2,3. – Dist.: Kv
 221. *Typha angustifolia* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 1,2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 222. *Typha latifolia* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 1,2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Clade eudicots

Amaranthaceae

223. *Amaranthus albus* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv
 224. *Amaranthus retroflexus* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 225. *Atriplex prostrata* Boucher ex DC. subsp. *latifolia* (Wahlenb.) Rauschert: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv
 226. *Atriplex sagittata* Borkh.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: . – Origin: As. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv
 227. *Atriplex tatarica* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv
 228. *Bassia laniflora* (S.G.Gmel.) A.J.Scott: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Med. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 229. *Chenopodium hybridum* (L.) S.Fuentes, Uotila & Borsch: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 230. *Chenopodium album* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 231. *Corispermum nitidum* Kit. ex Schult.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 232. *Lipandra polysperma* (L.) S.Fuentes, Uotila & Borsch: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv
 233. *Oxybasis × schulzeana* (Murr) Mosyakin: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euro?. – Dist.: Kv
 Note. The record of *Camphorosma annua* Pall. from a salt marsh in the vicinity of Khotsky village (Rogowicz 1869) clearly does not concern the territory of the Park.

Apiaceae

234. *Aegopodium podagraria* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 4,5,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 235. *Aethusa cynapium* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 236. *Angelica sylvestris* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 237. *Anthriscus sylvestris* (L.) Hoffm.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Multi. – Coen.: 6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 238. *Chaerophyllum bulbosum* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 4,5,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 239. *Chaerophyllum temulum* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 4,5,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

240. *Cicuta virosa* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 1,2,3. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 241. *Conium maculatum* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 242. *Daucus carota* L.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
Dichoropetalum carvifolia (Vill.) Pimenov & Kljuykov (= *Peucedanum carvifolia* Vill.): listed according to (Yarova 2015)
 243. *Eryngium campestre* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Med. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 244. *Eryngium planum* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 245. *Falcaria vulgaris* Bernh.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 246. *Heracleum sibiricum* L.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 247. *Oenanthe aquatica* (L.) Poir.: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 1,2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 248. *Ostericum palustre* (Besser) Besser: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Sib. – Coen.: 2,7. – Dist.: Kv
 249. *Pastinaca sativa* L. var. *sylvestris* (Mill.) Mérat: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Med. – Coen.: 6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 250. *Peucedanum cervaria* (L.) Lapeyr.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv
 251. *Peucedanum oreoselinum* (L.) Moench: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 252. *Peucedanum palustre* (L.) Moench: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 2,3. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 253. *Pimpinella saxifraga* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Sib. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 254. *Selinum carvifolia* (L.) L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 255. *Seseli annuum* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 256. *Seseli arenarium* M.Bieb.: Native. – L. f.: Perennial. – Range: Med. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv
 257. *Seseli campestre* Besser: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Med. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 258. *Silphiodaucus prutenicus* (L.) Spalik, Wojew., Banasiak, Piwczynski & Reduron: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 259. *Sium latifolium* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Sib. – Coen.: 2,3. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 260. *Taeniopetalum arenarium* (Waldst. & Kit.) V.N.Tikhom.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Steppe. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 261. *Torilis japonica* (Houtt.) DC.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Apocynaceae

262. *Asclepias syriaca* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: perennial. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 263. *Vinca minor* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 4,5,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 264. *Vincetoxicum hirundinaria* Medik.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Asteraceae

265. *Achillea pannonica* Scheele: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: N. Steppe. – Coen.: 5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 266. *Achillea salicifolia* Besser ex DC.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv
 267. *Achillea setacea* Waldst. & Kit.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 268. *Ambrosia artemisiifolia* L.: Alien(Erg.-Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 269. *Anthemis cotula* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 270. *Anthemis ruthenica* M.Bieb.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Steppe. – Coen.: 8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 271. *Arctium lappa* L.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 272. *Arctium nemorosum* Lej.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 4,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 273. *Arctium tomentosum* Mill.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 274. *Artemisia absinthium* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: perennial. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 275. *Artemisia austriaca* Jacq.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 6,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

276. *Artemisia marschalliana* Spreng.: Native. – L. f.: subshrub. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv. – Note. This species should also include *A. dniproica* Klokov, which is considered merely its glabrous form (Boiko, 2011), as well as the record of *A. campestris* L. (Yarova 2015), a species that does not occur reliably in Ukraine (Boiko, 2011)
277. *Artemisia scoparia* Waldst. & Kit.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv
278. *Artemisia vulgaris* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
279. *Bidens cernua* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
280. *Bidens connata* Muhl. ex Willd.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 2,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
281. *Bidens frondosa* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 2,3,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
282. *Bidens tripartita* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Multi. – Coen.: 2,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
283. *Carduus acanthoides* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
284. *Carduus crispus* L.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
285. *Carduus nutans* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 6, 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
286. *Carlina biebersteinii* Bernh. ex Hornem.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
287. *Centaurea borysthena* Gruner: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
288. *Centaurea cyanus* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
289. *Centaurea jacea* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
290. *Centaurea phrygia* subsp. *pseudophrygia* (C.A.Mey.) Gugler: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: N. Steppe. – Coen.: 5,6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
291. *Centaurea scabiosa* subsp. *apiculata* (Ledeb.) Mikheev: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Steppe. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv
292. *Chondrilla juncea* L.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Med. – Coen.: 6,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
293. *Chondrilla latifolia* M.Bieb.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Med. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
294. *Cichorium intybus* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: perennial. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
295. *Cirsium arvense* (L.) Scop. var. *arvense*: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,3,5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
C. arvense var. *setosum* (Willd.) Hohen.: Native
C. arvense var. *vestitum* Wimm. & Grab.: Native
296. *Cirsium canum* (L.) All.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: N. Steppe. – Coen.: 2,7. – Dist.: Kv
297. *Cirsium oleraceum* (L.) Scop.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 2,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
298. *Cirsium vulgare* (Savi) Ten.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
299. *Crepis foetida* L. subsp. *rhoeadifolia* (M.Bieb.) Čelak.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Med. – Coen.: 6,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
300. *Crepis tectorum* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
301. *Erechtites hieraciifolius* (L.) Raf. ex DC.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 2,3,4,5,7,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
302. *Erigeron acris* L. subsp. *acris*: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv
303. *Erigeron annuus* (L.) Desf.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 2,3,4,5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
304. *Erigeron canadensis* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
305. *Erigeron strigosus* Muhl. ex Willd.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
306. *Eupatorium cannabinum* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 2,3,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
307. *Euphrosyne xanthiifolia* (Nutt.) A.Gray: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

308. *Filago arvensis* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv
309. *Galinsoga parviflora* Cav.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
310. *Gnaphalium rossicum* Kirp.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Steppe. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
311. *Helianthus annuus* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv
312. *Helianthus tuberosus* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: perennial. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv
313. *Helichrysum arenarium* (L.) Moench: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
314. *Hieracium murorum* L. subsp. *sylvivagum* (Jord. ex Boreau) Greuter: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv
315. *Hieracium umbellatum* L. subsp. *umbellatum*: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
316. *Hieracium umbellatum* subsp. *filifolium* (Üksip) Tzvelev: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 5,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk. – Note: This narrow-leaved geographical race, which is confined to pine forests, is not recognized as an independent one in the current version of the *Plants of the World Online* database.
317. *Hypochaeris maculata* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Sib. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
318. *Hypochaeris radicata* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
319. *Inula helenium* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv
320. *Jacobaea borysthonica* (DC.) B.Nord. & Greuter: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
321. *Jacobaea erucifolia* (L.) G.Gaertn., B.Mey. & Scherb.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Sib. – Coen.: 5,6. – Dist.: Crk
322. *Jacobaea paludosa* (L.) G.Gaertn., B.Mey. & Scherb. subsp. *lanata* (Holub) B.Nord. & Greuter: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
323. *Jacobaea vulgaris* Gaertn.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 5,6,7,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
324. *Jurinea cyanoides* (L.) Rchb.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 6,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
325. *Lactuca muralis* (L.) E.Mey.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 4,5,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
326. *Lactuca quercina* L.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Med. – Coen.: 4,5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
327. *Lactuca saligna* L.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
328. *Lactuca serriola* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 4,5,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
329. *Lactuca tatarica* (L.) C.A.Mey.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: perennial. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
330. *Lapsana communis* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 4,5,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
331. *Matricaria chamomilla* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Euro. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
332. *Matricaria discoidea* DC.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
333. *Omalotheca sylvatica* (L.) Sch.Bip. & F.W.Schultz: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv
334. *Onopordum acanthium* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
335. *Pentanema britannica* (L.) D.Gut.Larr., Santos-Vicente, Anderb., E.Rico & M.M.Mart.Ort.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv
336. *Pentanema hirtum* (L.) D.Gut.Larr., Santos-Vicente, Anderb., E.Rico & M.M.Mart.Ort.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv
337. *Pentanema salicinum* (L.) D.Gut.Larr., Santos-Vicente, Anderb., E.Rico & M.M.Mart.Ort.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
338. *Petasites spurius* (Retz.) Rchb.f.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
339. *Picris hieracioides* L.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
340. *Pilosella auriculoides* (Láng) Arv.-Touv.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 6,7.

- Dist.: Kv
341. *Pilosella caespitosa* (Dumort.) P.D.Sell & C.West: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
342. *Pilosella cymosa* (L.) F.W.Schultz & Sch.Bip.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5,6,7,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
343. *Pilosella dubia* (L.) F.W.Schultz & Sch.Bip.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv
344. *Pilosella echioides* (Lum.) F.W.Schultz & Sch.Bip.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
345. *Pilosella floribunda* (Wimm. & Grab.) Fr.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5,6,7,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
346. *Pilosella glomerata* (Fr.) Fr.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5,6,7,8. – Dist.: Kv
347. *Pilosella officinarum* Vaill.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 5,6,7,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
348. *Pilosella onegensis* Norrl.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv
349. *Pilosella piloselloides* (Vill.) Soják subsp. *magyarica* (Peter) S.Bräut. & Greuter: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv
350. *Psephellus sumensis* (Kalen.) Greuter: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5,6,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
351. *Rudbeckia laciniata* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: perennial. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 7,9. – Dist.: Kv
352. *Scorzonera purpurea* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: N. Steppe. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv
353. *Scorzoneroides autumnalis* (L.) Moench: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
354. *Senecio vernalis* Waldst. & Kit.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Med. – Coen.: 5,6,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
355. *Senecio viscosus* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Origin: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 5,6,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
356. *Senecio vulgaris* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
357. *Serratula tinctoria* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
358. *Solidago canadensis* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: perennial. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
359. *Solidago virgaurea* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
360. *Sonchus arvensis* L. subsp. *uliginosus* (M.Bieb.) Nyman: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
361. *Sonchus asper* (L.) Hill: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
362. *Sonchus oleraceus* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
363. *Sonchus palustris* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
364. *Tanacetum corymbosum* (L.) Sch.Bip.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
365. *Tanacetum vulgare* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
366. *Taraxacum officinale* F.H.Wigg. s.l.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
367. *Taraxacum proximum* (Dahlst.) Dahlst.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 6, 7, 9. – Dist.: Kv
368. *Tephrosia integrifolia* (L.) Holub: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
369. *Tragopogon dubius* L. subsp. *major* (Jacq.) Vollm.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: N. Steppe (cited after Yarova 2015)
370. *Tragopogon orientalis* L.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Euro-Sib. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
371. *Tragopogon podolicus* (DC.) Nikitina: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: N. Steppe. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
372. *Tragopogon ucrainicus* Artemczuk: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

373. *Tripleurospermum inodorum* (L.) Sch.Bip.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
374. *Tussilago farfara* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 2,5,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
375. *Xanthium orientale* L. var. *album* (Widder) Adema & M.T.Jansen: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Euro. – Coen.: 2,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
376. *Xanthium strumarium* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv
 Note: Also reported were *Anthemis arvensis* L., *Centaurea arenaria* M.Bieb., *Crepis biennis* L., *Galatella linosyris* (L.) Rchb.f., *Hieracium umbrosum* Jord., *Pentanema asperum* (Poir.) G.V.Boiko & Korniy., *Scorzonera parviflora* Jacq., *Tripolium pannonicum* (Jacq.) Dobroc. (as *T. vulgare* Nees) (Rogowicz 1869; Yarova 2015). These records require confirmation within the current territory of the Park. However, the reference to *C. arenaria* most likely concerns *C. borysthena*, and *H. umbrosum* – *H. murorum* subsp. *sylvivagum*.
- Balsaminaceae**
377. *Impatiens noli-tangere* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
378. *Impatiens parviflora* DC.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 2,4,5,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
- Berberidaceae**
379. *Berberis vulgaris* L.: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 5,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
- Betulaceae**
380. *Alnus glutinosa* (L.) Gaertn.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
381. *Betula pendula* Roth: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 2,3,4,5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
382. *Betula pubescens* Ehrh.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 2,3. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
383. *Carpinus betulus* L.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 4,5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
384. *Corylus avellana* L.: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 4,5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
- Boraginaceae**
385. *Anchusa arvensis* (L.) M.Bieb.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
387. *Anchusa officinalis* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
386. *Anchusa procera* Besser ex Link: Native. – L. f.: biennial. – Range: Med (cited after Yarova 2015)
388. *Asperugo procumbens* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
389. *Buglossoides arvensis* (L.) I.M.Johnst.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
390. *Buglossoides rochelii* (Friv.) Stoyanov, Mátis & Sennikov (= *B. czernjajevii* (Klokov & Des.-Shost.) Czerep.): Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Steppe. – Coen.: 6,7,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
391. *Cynoglossum officinale* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
392. *Echium vulgare* L.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
393. *Lithospermum officinale* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv
394. *Myosotis arvensis* (L.) Hill: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
395. *Myosotis popovii* Dobroc.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Steppe. – Coen.: 5,6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
396. *Myosotis scorpioides* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,3. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
397. *Myosotis sparsiflora* J.C.Mikan ex Pohl: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,4,5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
398. *Myosotis stricta* Link ex Roem. & Schult.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 5,6,7,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
399. *Nonea pulla* (L.) DC.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 6,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
400. *Pulmonaria angustifolia* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5,6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
401. *Pulmonaria obscura* Dumort.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 4. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
402. *Symphytum officinale* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
- Brassicaceae**
403. *Alliaria petiolata* (M.Bieb.) Cavara & Grande: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 2,4,5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
404. *Alyssum alyssoides* (L.) L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Med. – Coen.: 6,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
405. *Arabidopsis arenosa* (L.) Lawalrée: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7,8,9. –

- Dist.: Kv, Crk
406. *Arabidopsis thaliana* (L.) Heynh.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 6,7,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
407. *Armoracia rusticana* P.Gaertn., B.Mey. & Scherb.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: perennial. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
408. *Barbarea stricta* Andr. ex Besser: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
409. *Berteroa incana* (L.) DC.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
410. *Brassica napus* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
411. *Bunias orientalis* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 6,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
412. *Brassica rapa* L. var. *oleifera* (DC.) Lej. & Courtois: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: As (cited after Yarova 2015)
413. *Capsella bursa-pastoris* (L.) Medik.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
414. *Cardamine impatiens* L.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 4. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
415. *Cardamine parviflora* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 2,3. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
416. *Cardamine pratensis* L. subsp. *paludosa* (Knaf) Čelak.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 3. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
417. *Descurainia sophia* (L.) Webb ex Prantl: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
418. *Draba nemorosa* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 5,6,7,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
419. *Draba verna* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 5,6,7,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
420. *Erysimum canum* (Pill. & Mitterp.) Polatschek: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euro (cited after Yarova 2015)
421. *Erysimum cheiranthoides* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
422. *Erysimum marschallianum* Andr. ex DC.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: N. Steppe. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv
423. *Lepidium densiflorum* Schrad.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
424. *Lepidium ruderale* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
425. *Mutarda arvensis* (L.) D.A.German (= *Sinapis arvensis* L.): Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
426. *Raphanus raphanistrum* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
427. *Rorippa amphibia* (L.) Besser: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 1,2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
428. *Rorippa palustris* (L.) Besser: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Multi. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
429. *Rorippa sylvestris* (L.) Besser: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 2,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
430. *Sisymbrium altissimum* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
431. *Sisymbrium loeselii* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
432. *Sisymbrium officinale* (L.) Scop.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
433. *Sisymbrium polymorphum* (Murray) Roth: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Steppe. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv
434. *Thlaspi arvense* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
435. *Turritis glabra* L.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
- Campanulaceae**
436. *Campanula bononiensis* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv
437. *Campanula glomerata* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
438. *Campanula persicifolia* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 4,5,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
439. *Campanula rapunculoides* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

440. *Campanula rapunculus* L.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
441. *Campanula rotundifolia* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 5,6,7,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
442. *Campanula sibirica* L.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv
443. *Campanula trachelium* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 4. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
444. *Jasione montana* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 5,6,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
- Cannabaceae**
445. *Cannabis sativa* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
446. *Humulus lupulus* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,3,5,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
- Caprifoliaceae**
447. *Knautia arvensis* (L.) Coult.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
448. *Lonicera tatarica* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: shrub. – Origin: Euras. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
449. *Scabiosa ochroleuca* L.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
450. *Succisa pratensis* Moench: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Sib. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv
451. *Valeriana locusta* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
452. *Valeriana officinalis* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
453. *Valeriana stolonifera* Czern.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv
- Caryophyllaceae**
454. *Arenaria serpyllifolia* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 5,6,7,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
455. *Cerastium arvense* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv
456. *Cerastium holosteoides* Fr.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,7,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
457. *Cerastium semidecandrum* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 6,7,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
458. *Dianthus arenarius* L. subsp. *pseudosquarrosus* (Novák) Kleopow: Native. – L. f.: subshrub. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
459. *Dianthus borbasii* Vandas: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 6,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
460. *Dianthus chinensis* L. (= *D. pineticola* Kleopow): Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv
461. *Eremogone procera* (Spreng.) Rchb.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: N. Steppe. – Coen.: 5,6,8. – Dist.: Kv
462. *Gypsophila paniculata* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
463. *Herniaria glabra* L.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 5,6,7,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
464. *Herniaria polygama* J.Gay: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: N. Steppe. – Coen.: 5,6,7,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
465. *Holosteum umbellatum* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 6,7,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
466. *Moehringia trinervia* (L.) Clairv.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 4,5,7,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
467. *Psammophiliella muralis* (L.) Ikonn.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
468. *Rabelera holostea* (L.) M.T.Sharple & E.A.Tripp: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 4,5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
469. *Sagina procumbens* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
470. *Saponaria officinalis* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: perennial. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
471. *Scleranthus annuus* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
472. *Scleranthus perennis* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
473. *Silene baccifera* (L.) Roth: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 2,4,5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

474. *Silene borysthena* (Gruner) Walters: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
Silene chersonensis (Zapař.) Kleopow: listed according to (Yarova 2015)
475. *Silene flos-cuculi* (L.) Greuter & Burdet: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv
476. *Silene latifolia* Poir. subsp. *alba* (Miller) Greuter & Burdet: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
477. *Silene noctiflora* L.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Euro-Sib. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv
478. *Silene nutans* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
479. *Silene tatarica* (L.) Pers.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 6,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
480. *Silene vulgaris* (Moench) Garcke: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
481. *Spergula arvensis* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
482. *Spergula morisonii* Boreau: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv
483. *Spergularia rubra* (L.) J.Presl & C.Presl: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
484. *Stellaria aquatica* (L.) Scop.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,3,4,5,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
485. *Stellaria graminea* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,7,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
486. *Stellaria media* (L.) Vill.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Multi. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
487. *Stellaria nemorum* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 4. – Dist.: Kv
488. *Stellaria palustris* Ehrh. ex Hoffm.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 3. – Dist.: Kv
489. *Viscaria vulgaris* Bernh.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
Note. *Stellaria alsine* Grimm. was also reported (Yarova 2015), but the occurrence of this species requires confirmation
- Celastraceae**
490. *Euonymus europaeus* L.: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 2,4,5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
491. *Euonymus verrucosus* Scop.: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 4,5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
- Ceratophyllaceae**
492. *Ceratophyllum demersum* L.: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: Multi. – Coen.: 1. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
493. *Ceratophyllum submersum* L.: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 1. – Dist.: Kv
- Convolvulaceae**
494. *Calystegia sepium* (L.) R.Br.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Multi. – Coen.: 2,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
495. *Convolvulus arvensis* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
496. *Cuscuta epithimum* (L.) L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
497. *Cuscuta lupuliformis* Krock.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
- Cornaceae**
498. *Cornus sanguinea* L. subsp. *sanguinea*: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 2,4,5,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
499. *Cornus sanguinea* subsp. *australis* (C.A.Mey.) Jáv.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: shrub. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 2,4,5,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
- Crassulaceae**
500. *Hylotelephium maximum* (L.) Holub subsp. *maximum*: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 4,5,6,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
501. *Hylotelephium maximum* subsp. *ruprechtii* (Jalas) Dostál: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
502. *Sedum acre* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
503. *Sedum pallidum* M.Bieb.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: perennial. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv
504. *Sedum sexangulare* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: perennial. – Origin: Euro. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
505. *Sempervivum ruthenicum* Schnittsp. & C.B.Lehm.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Cucurbitaceae

506. *Cucurbita pepo* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv
507. *Echinocystis lobata* (Michx.) Torr. & A.Gray: Alien(Erg.-Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Droseraceae

508. *Aldrovanda vesiculosa* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Multi. – Coen.: 1. – Dist.: Kv
509. *Drosera rotundifolia* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 3. – Dist.: Kv. – Note. The species was first cited for a peat bog in the vicinity of Khotsky village by A. Rogowicz (1869)

Elaeagnaceae

510. *Elaeagnus angustifolia* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: tree. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Ericaceae

511. *Calluna vulgaris* (L.) Hull: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
512. *Chimaphila umbellata* (L.) W.P.C.Barton: Native. – L. f.: subshrub. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
513. *Monotropa hypopitys* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
514. *Orthilia secunda* (L.) House: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
515. *Pyrola minor* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 3,5. – Dist.: Kv
516. *Pyrola rotundifolia* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 3,5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
517. *Vaccinium myrtillus* L.: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv

Euphorbiaceae

518. *Euphorbia cyparissias* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
519. *Euphorbia illirica* Lam.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Med. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv
520. *Euphorbia saratoui* Ardoino: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,4,5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
521. *Euphorbia seguieriana* Neck.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
Note. *Euphorbia palustris* L. listed according to (Yarova 2015)

Fabaceae

522. *Amorpha fruticosa* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: shrub. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 2,4,5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
523. *Astragalus dasyanthus* Pall.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Steppe. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv
524. *Astragalus glycyphyllos* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
525. *Astragalus onobrychis* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 6,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
526. *Astragalus varius* S.G.Gmel.: Native. – L. f.: subshrub. – Range: Steppe. – Coen.: 6,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
527. *Caragana arborescens* Lam.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: shrub. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
528. *Chamaecytisus austriacus* (L.) Link: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: N. Steppe. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv
529. *Chamaecytisus ruthenicus* (Fisch. ex Wol.) Klásk.: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5,6,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
530. *Coronilla varia* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
531. *Genista tinctoria* L.: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: Euro-Sib. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
532. *Lathyrus palustris* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv
533. *Lathyrus pratensis* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv
534. *Lathyrus sylvestris* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv
535. *Lathyrus tuberosus* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: perennial. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 7,9. – Dist.: Kv
536. *Lathyrus vernus* (L.) Bernh.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 4. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
537. *Lotus corniculatus* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
538. *Lotus stepposus* Kramina: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Steppe. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
539. *Lupinus polyphyllus* Lindl.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: perennial. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 7,9. – Dist.: Kv
540. *Medicago falcata* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
541. *Medicago lupulina* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
542. *Melilotus albus* Medik.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

543. *Melilotus officinalis* (L.) Lam.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
544. *Onobrychis arenaria* (Kit.) DC.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv
545. *Robinia pseudoacacia* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: tree. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
546. *Trifolium alpestre* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5,6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
547. *Trifolium arvense* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 6,7,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
548. *Trifolium aureum* Pollich: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
549. *Trifolium campestre* Schreb.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
550. *Trifolium dubium* Sibth.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
551. *Trifolium fragiferum* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv
552. *Trifolium hybridum* L. subsp. *hybridum*: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: perennial. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv
553. *Trifolium hybridum* subsp. *elegans* (Savi) Asch. & Graebn.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: perennial. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv
554. *Trifolium medium* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
555. *Trifolium montanum* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
556. *Trifolium pratense* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
557. *Trifolium repens* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 5,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
558. *Vicia cracca* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
559. *Vicia hirsuta* (L.) Gray: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
560. *Vicia sativa* L. subsp. *nigra* Ehrh.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 7,9. – Dist.: Kv
561. *Vicia sepium* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
562. *Vicia tetrasperma* (L.) Schreb.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
563. *Vicia villosa* Roth: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
- Note. Also reported were *Astragalus cicer* L. and *A. sulcatus* L. (Yarova 2015), but these records require confirmation.

Fagaceae

564. *Quercus robur* L.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 2,4,5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
565. *Quercus rubra* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: tree. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Gentianaceae

566. *Centaurium erythraea* Rafn: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv

Geraniaceae

567. *Erodium cicutarium* (L.) L'Her.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
568. *Geranium collinum* Stephan ex Willd.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv
569. *Geranium molle* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv
570. *Geranium palustre* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv
571. *Geranium pratense* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv
572. *Geranium pusillum* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
573. *Geranium robertianum* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,4,5,7,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
574. *Geranium sanguineum* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
575. *Geranium sibiricum* L.: Alien(Erg.-Xen.). – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Origin: As(Sib). – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv

Grossulariaceae

576. *Ribes nigrum* L.: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv
577. *Ribes rubrum* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: shrub. – Origin: Euro. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv
578. *Ribes uva-crispa* L.: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Haloragaceae

579. *Myriophyllum spicatum* L.: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: Multi (cited after Yarova 2015)
580. *Myriophyllum verticillatum* L.: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 1. – Dist.: Kv

Hypericaceae

581. *Hypericum elegans* Stephan ex Willd.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Steppe. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv

582. *Hypericum hirsutum* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 4,5,6. – Dist.: Kv

583. *Hypericum montanum* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 4,5,6. – Dist.: Crk

584. *Hypericum perforatum* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Juglandaceae

585. *Juglans regia* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: tree. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Lamiaceae

586. *Ajuga genevensis* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

587. *Ajuga reptans* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 2,4,5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

588. *Ballota nigra* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: perennial. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

589. *Betonica officinalis* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 4,5,6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

590. *Clinopodium acinos* (L.) Kuntze: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 5,6,7,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

591. *Clinopodium vulgare* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

592. *Galeopsis bifida* Boenn.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

593. *Galeopsis pubescens* Besser: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

594. *Galeopsis tetrahit* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

595. *Glechoma hederacea* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 4,5,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

596. *Glechoma hirsuta* Waldst. & Kit.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Med. – Coen.: 4,5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

597. *Lamium amplexicaule* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

598. *Lamium galeobdolon* (L.) L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 4,5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

599. *Lamium maculatum* (L.) L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 4,5,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

600. *Lamium purpureum* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

601. *Leonurus quinquelobatus* Gilib.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

602. *Lycopus europaeus* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 2,3,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

603. *Mentha aquatica* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

604. *Mentha arvensis* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,3,5,7. – Dist.: Kv

605. *Mentha × verticillata* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 2,7. – Dist.: Kv

606. *Nepeta cataria* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: perennial. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv

607. *Nepeta nuda* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv

608. *Origanum vulgare* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 4,5,6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

609. *Prunella grandiflora* (L.) Turra: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

610. *Prunella vulgaris* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 2,4,5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

611. *Salvia nemorosa* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: N. Steppe. – Coen.: 5,6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

612. *Salvia nutans* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Steppe. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv

613. *Salvia pratensis* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5,6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

614. *Salvia verticillata* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv

615. *Scutellaria galericulata* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 2,3,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

616. *Scutellaria hastifolia* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 2,3. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

617. *Stachys annua* (L.) L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

618. *Stachys palustris* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,3,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

619. *Stachys recta* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 5,6,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

620. *Stachys sylvatica* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 4. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

621. *Teucrium chamaedrys* L.: Native. – L. f.: subshrub. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 5,6,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

622. *Thymus pallasianus* Heinr.Braun: Native. – L. f.: subshrub. – Range: Steppe. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

623. *Thymus pannonicus* All.: Native. – L. f.: subshrub. – Range: Steppe. – Coen.: 6,7,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

624. *Thymus × tschernjaievii* Klokov & Des.-Shost.: Native. – L. f.: subshrub. – Range: Steppe. – Coen.:

8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 Note. *Thymus serpyllum* L. was also cited (Yarova 2015), but the occurrence of this species requires confirmation.
- Lentibulariaceae**
 625. *Utricularia minor* L.: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 1,3. – Dist.: Kv
 626. *Utricularia × neglecta* Lehm.: Native?. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: Multi. – Coen.: 1. – Dist.: Kv
 627. *Utricularia vulgaris* L.: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 1. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
- Linaceae**
 628. *Linum perenne* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
- Lythraceae**
 629. *Lythrum salicaria* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 2,3. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 630. *Trapa natans* L. var. *borysthena* (V.N.Vassil.) Tzelev: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 1. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
- Malvaceae**
 631. *Alcea rosea* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: perennial. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv
 632. *Althaea officinalis* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: perennial. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 7,9. – Dist.: Kv
 633. *Malva neglecta* Wallr.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 634. *Malva pusilla* Sm.: Alien(Erg.-Xen.). – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Origin: Euras. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 635. *Malva thuringiaca* (L.) Vis.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 636. *Tilia cordata* Mill.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 2,4,5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 637. *Tilia platyphyllos* Scop. subsp. *cordifolia* (Besser) C.K.Schneid.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: tree. – Origin: Euro. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv
- Menyanthaceae**
 638. *Menyanthes trifoliata* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 3. – Dist.: Kv
- Moraceae**
 639. *Morus alba* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: tree. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk. – Note. The record of *M. nigra* L. (Yarova 2015) probably also refers to this species.
- Nyctaginaceae**
 640. *Mirabilis jalapa* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv
- Oleaceae**
 641. *Fraxinus excelsior* L.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 2,4,5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 642. *Fraxinus pennsylvanica* Marshall: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: tree. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 2,4,5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 643. *Ligustrum vulgare* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: shrub. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 644. *Syringa vulgaris* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: shrub. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
- Onagraceae**
 645. *Epilobium angustifolium* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 646. *Epilobium hirsutum* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 2,3. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 647. *Epilobium palustre* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 2,3. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 648. *Epilobium parviflorum* Schreb.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PArct (cited after Yarova 2015)
 649. *Epilobium roseum* (Schreb.) Schreb.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,3,4,5,7. – Dist.: Kv
 650. *Epilobium tetragonum* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 2,3,4,5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 651. *Oenothera biennis* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 5,6,7,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
- Orobanchaceae**
 652. *Melampyrum nemorosum* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 4,5,6. – Dist.: Kv
 653. *Melampyrum pratense* L. subsp. *pratense*: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

654. *Melampyrum pratense* subsp. *laciniatum* (Kosh. & V.J.Zinger) Tzvelev: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 4,5,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
655. *Odontites vulgaris* Moench: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,7,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
656. *Orobancha caryophyllacea* Sm.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv
657. *Pedicularis palustris* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 3. – Dist.: Kv
658. *Rhinanthus minor* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv

Oxalidaceae

659. *Oxalis dillenii* Jacq.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: perennial. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
660. *Oxalis stricta* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: perennial. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Papaveraceae

661. *Chelidonium majus* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 4,5,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
662. *Corydalis solida* (L.) Clairv.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 4. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
663. *Eschscholzia californica* Cham.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv
664. *Papaver rhoeas* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Phytolaccaceae

Phytolacca americana L.: listed according to (Yarova 2015). Perhaps this record refers to *P. acinosa* Roxb. We observed this species in the area adjacent to the Park, but not within the Park itself.

Plantaginaceae

665. *Callitriche* sp.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Bor?. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv
666. *Digitalis grandiflora* Mill.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 4,5,6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
667. *Gratiola officinalis* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Sib. – Coen.: 5,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
668. *Linaria genistifolia* (L.) Mill.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
669. *Linaria vulgaris* Mill.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
670. *Plantago indica* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
671. *Plantago lanceolata* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
672. *Plantago major* L. subsp. *major*: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
673. *Plantago major* subsp. *intermedia* (Gilib.) Lange: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
674. *Plantago media* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
675. *Veronica anagallis-aquatica* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv
676. *Veronica arvensis* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 5,6,7,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
677. *Veronica beccabunga* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
678. *Veronica chamaedrys* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,4,5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
679. *Veronica dillenii* Crantz: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 6,7,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
680. *Veronica longifolia* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 2,3,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
681. *Veronica officinalis* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 4,5,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
682. *Veronica polita* Fr.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
683. *Veronica persica* Poir.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: As (cited after Yarova 2015)
684. *Veronica scutellata* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
685. *Veronica serpyllifolia* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 4,5,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
686. *Veronica spicata* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
687. *Veronica sublobata* M.A.Fisch.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
688. *Veronica verna* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 6,7,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
- Note. The record of *Plantago salsa* Pall. (as *P. maritima* L.) from the vicinity of Khotsky village (Rogowicz 1869) clearly does not concern the territory of the Park

Polygonaceae

689. *Fallopia convolvulus* (L.) Á.Löve: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 2,4,5,6,7,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
690. *Fallopia dumetorum* (L.) Holub: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,4,5,6,7,8,9. – Dist.:

- Kv, Crk
691. *Persicaria amphibia* (L.) Delarbre: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 1,2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
692. *Persicaria hydropiper* (L.) Delarbre: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 2,3,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
693. *Persicaria lapathifolia* (L.) Delarbre: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,3,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
694. *Persicaria maculosa* Gray: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 2,3,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
695. *Persicaria minor* (Huds.) Opiz: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,3,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
696. *Persicaria mitis* (Schrank) Assenov: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 2,3,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
697. *Polygonum arenarium* Waldst. & Kit.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Crk
698. *Polygonum aviculare* L. subsp. *aviculare*: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
699. *Polygonum aviculare* subsp. *neglectum* (Besser) Arcang.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
700. *Polygonum novoascanicum* Klokov: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Steppe. – Coen.: 6,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
701. *Rumex acetosa* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
702. *Rumex acetosella* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 5,6,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
703. *Rumex confertus* Willd.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
704. *Rumex crispus* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,5,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
705. *Rumex hydrolapathum* Huds.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
706. *Rumex maritimus* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv
707. *Rumex obtusifolius* L. subsp. *sylvestris* (Lam.) Čelak.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
708. *Rumex patientia* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: perennial. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv
709. *Rumex thyriflorus* Fingerh.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,7,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
- Portulacaceae**
710. *Portulaca oleracea* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
- Primulaceae**
711. *Hottonia palustris* L.: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv
712. *Lysimachia arvensis* (L.) U.Manns & Anderb.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med (cited after Yarova 2015)
- Lysimachia minima* (L.) U.Manns & Anderb.: listed according to (Rogowicz 1869)
713. *Lysimachia nummularia* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 2,4,5,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
714. *Lysimachia thyriflora* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 3. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
715. *Lysimachia vulgaris* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,3,5,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
- Ranunculaceae**
716. *Aconitum anthora* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv
717. *Adonis vernalis* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: N. Steppe. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv
718. *Anemonoides ranunculoides* (L.) Holub: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 4. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
719. *Anemonoides sylvestris* (L.) Galasso, Banfi & Soldano: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv
720. *Caltha palustris* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 2,3. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
721. *Clematis recta* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: N. Steppe. – Coen.: 4,5,6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
722. *Delphinium consolida* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
- Delphinium cuneatum* Spreng. (= *D. elatum* auct. non L.) was reported from the vicinity of Khotsky village (Rogowicz 1869; Yarova 2015)

723. *Pulsatilla patens* (L.) Mill.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
724. *Pulsatilla pratensis* (L.) Mill.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5,6,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
725. *Ranunculus acris* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
Ranunculus auricomus L.: listed according to (Yarova 2015)
726. *Ranunculus cassubicus* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 4. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
727. *Ranunculus ficaria* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 4. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
728. *Ranunculus flammula* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 3. – Dist.: Kv
729. *Ranunculus lingua* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 3. – Dist.: Kv
730. *Ranunculus polyanthemos* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
731. *Ranunculus repens* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,3,5,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
732. *Ranunculus sceleratus* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
733. *Ranunculus trichophyllus* Chaix: Native. – L. f.: aquatic. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 1. – Dist.: Kv
734. *Thalictrum flavum* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv
735. *Thalictrum lucidum* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv
736. *Thalictrum minus* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6. – Dist.: Kv
737. *Thalictrum simplex* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6. – Dist.: Kv
- Rhamnaceae**
738. *Frangula alnus* Mill.: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,3,5,7,. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
739. *Rhamnus cathartica* L.: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
- Rosaceae**
740. *Agrimonia eupatoria* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 5,6,7,. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
741. *Agrimonia pilosa* Ledeb.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv
742. *Agrimonia procera* Wallr.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
743. *Amelanchier × spicata* (Lam.) K.Koch: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: shrub. – Origin: anthrop. – Coen.: 5,9. – Dist.: Kv
744. *Argentina anserina* (L.) Rydb.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Multi. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
745. *Comarum palustre* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 3. – Dist.: Kv
746. *Crataegus × kyrtostyla* Fingerh.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv
747. *Crataegus meyeri* Pojark.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv
748. *Crataegus monogyna* Jacq.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
749. *Crataegus rhipidophylla* Gand.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
750. *Filipendula ulmaria* (L.) Maxim.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,3. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
751. *Filipendula vulgaris* Moench: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 5,6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
752. *Fragaria vesca* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
753. *Geum urbanum* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 2,4,5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
754. *Malus domestica* (Suckow) Borkh.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: tree. – Origin: anthrop. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
755. *Malus sylvestris* (L.) Mill.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
756. *Physocarpus opulifolius* (L.) Maxim.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: shrub. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
757. *Potentilla alba* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
758. *Potentilla argentea* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,7,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
759. *Potentilla erecta* (L.) Roesch.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 5,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
760. *Potentilla incana* P.Gaertn., B.Mey. & Scherb.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 7,8. – Dist.: Kv
761. *Potentilla inclinata* Vill.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv
762. *Potentilla intermedia* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Sib. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
763. *Potentilla neglecta* Baumg.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 7,9. – Dist.: Kv
764. *Potentilla reptans* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: PARct. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

765. *Potentilla thyrsoflora* Hülsen ex Zimmeter: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro (cited after Yarova 2015)
766. *Prunus armeniaca* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: tree. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
767. *Prunus avium* (L.) L.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 4. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
768. *Prunus cerasifera* Ehrh.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: tree. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
769. *Prunus cerasus* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: shrub. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv
770. *Prunus domestica* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: tree. – Origin: anthrop. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
771. *Prunus fruticosa* Pall.: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: N. Steppe. – Coen.: 5,6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
772. *Prunus padus* L.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
773. *Prunus serotina* Ehrh.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: tree. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 4,5,6,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
774. *Prunus spinosa* L. subsp. *dasyphylla* (Schur) Domin: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
775. *Prunus tenella* Batsch.: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: Steppe. – Coen.: 7. – Dist.: Kv
776. *Pyrus communis* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: tree. – Origin: anthrop. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
777. *Pyrus pyraeaster* (L.) Burgsd.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv
778. *Rosa canina* L.: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
779. *Rosa caryophyllacea* Besser: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: Med. – Coen.: 5,6. – Dist.: Crk
780. *Rubus balticus* (Focke) E.H.L.Krause: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: shrub. – Origin: Euro. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Crk
781. *Rubus caesius* L.: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 2,4,5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
782. *Rubus × idaeoides* Ruthe: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 4,5,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
783. *Rubus idaeus* L.: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 2,4,5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
784. *Rubus polonicus* Weston: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 2,4,5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
785. *Rubus saxatilis* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
Rubus × suberectifolius Sudre (sub nom. *R. corylifolius* Besser): was reported from the vicinity of Khotzky village (Rogowicz 1869)
786. *Sorbus aucuparia* L.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 2,3,5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
Note. *Rosa glauca* Pourr. was also cited (Yarova 2015).

Rubiaceae

787. *Asperula tinctoria* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv
788. *Cruciata glabra* (L.) Opiz: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Sib. – Coen.: 4,5,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
789. *Cynanchica graveolens* (M.Bieb. ex Schult. & Schult.f.) P.Caputo & Del Guacchio: Native. – L. f.: subshrub. – Range: Steppe. – Coen.: 8. – Dist.: Kv
790. *Cynanchica pyrenaica* (L.) P.Caputo & Del Guacchio subsp. *cynanchica* (L.) P.Caputo & Del Guacchio: Native. – L. f.: subshrub. – Range: Euro-Med (cited after Yarova 2015)
791. *Galium aparine* L.: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 2,4,5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
792. *Galium boreale* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 5,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
793. *Galium odoratum* (L.) Scop.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 4. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
794. *Galium palustre* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Bor. – Coen.: 2,3,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
795. *Galium rivale* (Sm.) Griseb.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 3, 7. – Dist.: Kv
796. *Galium rubioides* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
797. *Galium verum* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
Note. *Galium trifidum* L. was also cited (Yarova 2015), but the occurrence of this species requires confirmation

Rutaceae

798. *Ptelea trifoliata* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: shrub. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Salicaceae

799. *Populus alba* L.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 2,5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
800. *Populus × canadensis* Moench: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: tree. – Origin: anthrop. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv
801. *Populus × canescens* (Aiton) Sm.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 2,5. – Dist.: Kv
802. *Populus nigra* L.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 2,5,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
803. *Populus tremula* L.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 2,3,4,5,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
804. *Salix acutifolia* Willd.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 7,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

805. *Salix alba* L.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 2,5,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 806. *Salix aurita* L.: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 3. – Dist.: Kv
 807. *Salix caprea* L.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,4,5,6,7,. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 808. *Salix cinerea* L.: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,3,7,. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 809. *Salix × fragilis* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: tree. – Origin: anthrop. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 810. *Salix pentandra* L.: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,3. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 811. *Salix rosmarinifolia* L.: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,3,5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
Salix triandra L.: listed according to (Yarova 2015)

Santalaceae

812. *Thesium ebracteatum* Hayne: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv
 813. *Thesium linophyllum* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv
 814. *Thesium ramosum* Hayne: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6. – Dist.: Kv
 815. *Viscum album* L. subsp. *album*: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 2,4,5,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Sapindaceae

816. *Acer campestre* L.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 4,5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 817. *Acer negundo* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: tree. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 2,4,5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 818. *Acer platanoides* L.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 4,5,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 819. *Acer pseudoplatanus* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: tree. – Origin: Euro. – Coen.: 2,4,5,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 820. *Acer tataricum* L.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 821. *Aesculus hippocastanum* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: tree. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Scrophulariaceae

822. *Scrophularia nodosa* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,3,4,5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 823. *Verbascum blattaria* L.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Med. – Coen.: 6. – Dist.: Kv
 824. *Verbascum densiflorum* Bertol.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv
 825. *Verbascum lychnitis* L.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: PArct. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 826. *Verbascum phlomoides* L.: Native. – L. f.: biennial/short-lived. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Solanaceae

827. *Hyoscyamus niger* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 828. *Solanum dulcamara* L.: Native. – L. f.: liana. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 829. *Solanum nigrum* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
Solanum nigrum var. *schultesii* (Opiz) Rouy: Dist.: Kv

Ulmaceae

830. *Ulmus glabra* Huds.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 2,45,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 831. *Ulmus laevis* Pall.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 2,4,5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 832. *Ulmus minor* Mill.: Native. – L. f.: tree. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 4,6. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Urticaceae

833. *Urtica dioica* L. subsp. *dioica*: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,3,4,5,6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 834. *Urtica dioica* subsp. *pubescens* (Ledeb.) Domin: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 2. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 835. *Urtica kioviensis* Rogow.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 1,2. – Dist.: Kv
 836. *Urtica urens* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Verbenaceae

837. *Verbena officinalis* L.: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: perennial. – Origin: As (cited after Yarova 2015)

Viburnaceae

838. *Adoxa moschatellina* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Hol. – Coen.: 4,5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 839. *Sambucus ebulus* L.: Native?. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk
 840. *Sambucus nigra* L.: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 4,5,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

841. *Sambucus racemosa* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: shrub. – Origin: Euro. – Coen.: 5,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

842. *Viburnum opulus* L.: Native. – L. f.: shrub. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 2,5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Violaceae

843. *Viola arvensis* Murray: Alien(Xen.). – L. f.: annual. – Origin: Med. – Coen.: 6,7,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

844. *Viola canina* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

845. *Viola hirta* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 4,5,6,7. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

846. *Viola mirabilis* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 4. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

847. *Viola odorata* L.: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euro-Med. – Coen.: 4,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

848. *Viola rupestris* F.W.Schmidt: Native. – L. f.: perennial. – Range: Euras. – Coen.: 5,6,8. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

849. *Viola tricolor* L. subsp. *matutina* (Klokov) Valentine: Native. – L. f.: annual. – Range: Euro. – Coen.: 5,6,7,8,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

Vitaceae

850. *Parthenocissus inserta* (A.Kern.) Fritsch: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: liana. – Origin: Am. – Coen.: 4,5,9. – Dist.: Kv, Crk

851. *Vitis vinifera* L.: Alien(Erg.). – L. f.: liana. – Origin: As. – Coen.: 4,5,9. – Dist.: Kv

Cultivated plants

Chaenomeles speciosa (Sweet) Nakai

Malus toringo (Siebold) de Vriese

Pinus banksiana Lamb.

Spiraea salicifolia L.

Symphotrichum novae-angliae (L.) G.L.Nesom

Vitis labrusca L.

Ergasiophgophytes found along the border with the Park territory

Amaranthus cruentus L.

Anethum graveolens L.

Atriplex hortensis L.

Calendula officinalis L.

Cosmos bipinnatus Cav.

Cucurbita maxima Duchesne

Cucurbita moschata Duchesne

Ipomoea purpurea (L.) Roth

Phytolacca acinosa

Prunus persica (L.) Batsch

Rhus typhina L.

Ribes aureum Pursh

Solanum lycopersicum L.

Solanum tuberosum L.

Tanacetum parthenium (L.) Sch.Bip.

Thladiantha dubia Bunge

Verbesina encelioides (Cav.) Benth. & Hook.f. ex A.Gray

Zea mays L.